
The Mechanism of the 2-Vectors 3-Poles and the Quadrature of the Two Conjugate Circles of Photons

By

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Abstract:

From [40]–The Special Problems of Euclidean Geometry [47] consist the, *Moulds of Quantization*, of E-Geometry in it, to become → Monad, through mould of Space – Anti-space in itself, which is the material dipole in inner monad Structure and which is identical with the Electromagnetic cycloidal field → Linearly through the mould of the Parallel Theorem [44-45], which are the equal distances between Points of Parallel and line → In Plane, through mould of Squaring the circle [46], where the two equal and Perpendicular monad-Vectors consist a Plane acquiring the common Plane-meter, π , → and in Space (volume) through mould of the Duplication of the Cube [46], where any two Unequal Perpendicular monads acquire the common Space-meter $^3\sqrt{2}$, to be twice each other, as analytically all methods are Proved and explained. [44-47]

The Unification of → Space and Energy ← becomes through [STPL] Geometrical Mould Mechanism of Elements, the minimum Energy-Quanta, In monads → Particles, Anti-Particles, Bosons, Gravity – Force, Gravity – Field, Photons, Dark Matter, and Dark Energy, consisting the Material Dipoles in inner monad Structures i.e., the innate Electromagnetic Cycloidal Field of monads ← [39-41]

Euclid's elements consist of assuming a small set of intuitively appealing axioms, Proving many other Propositions. Because no one until [9] succeeded to prove the Parallel Postulate by means of pure Geometric Logic, many self-consistent non- Euclidean geometries have been discovered, based on Definitions, Axioms Postulates, in order that none of them contradicts any of the other Postulates. It was Proved [39], that the only Space - Energy

Geometry is Euclidean , agreeing with the Physical reality , on unit $AB \equiv \text{Segment} \equiv \text{Vector}$ which is The Electromagnetic field of the Quantized on \overline{AB} Energy Space Vector of Angular Momentum = Spin , on the contrary to the General relativity of Space-time which is based on the rays of the non-Euclidean Geometries to the limited velocity of light in Planck's cavity . Euclidean Geometry elucidated the definitions of its geometry-content , i.e. { [for Point , Segment , Straight Line , Plane , Volume, Space [S] , Anti-space [AS] , Sub -space [SS] , Cave , The Space-Anti-Space Mechanism of the Six-Triple-Points-Line , that Produces and transfers Points of Spaces , Anti-Spaces and Sub-Spaces in a Common Inertial Sub-Space , and a cylinder ,in Gravity field [MFMF] Particles]} and describes the Space-Energy vacuum beyond Plank's length level [Gravity's Length $3,969.10^{-62}$ m] , reaching the absolute Point $= L_v = e^{i(\frac{N\pi}{2})} b=10^{-N} = -\infty \text{ m} = 0 \text{ m}$, which is nothing , and the Absolute Primary Neutral Space [PNS] = cave [$r = 10^{-35} \sim 10^{-62}$ m [43-46] .

In Mechanics , The Gravity-cave *Energy Volume quantity* $|\bar{c}| \equiv [wr]$ is doubled , and is Quantized in Planck's- cave Space quantity $(h/2\pi) = \text{The Spin} = 2.[wr]^3 \rightarrow \text{i.e. Energy Space quantity } [wr]$ is Quantized , *doubled* , and becomes the Space quantity h/π following Euclidean Space-mould of *Duplication of the cube*, in Sphere volume $V = (4\pi/3).[wr]^3$ and follows the *Squaring of the circle* π , and in Sub-Space-Sphere volume $^3\sqrt{2}$, as *Trisection* . In article [123] , are given on the **2-Vectors , 3-Poles Rotating Squares Mechanism** , such the Geometrical as the Mechanical Proof , by using the **Conjugate circles of Polhode and Herpolhode** which consist the Spin of Photons and which is their motion . The frequency needed for the velocity vector \bar{c} to rotate , is used the Kepler's **Unit of Time** $k = f_e^2 a^3$, where $a = \lambda / 2$, and which is **the clock** measuring the changes of motions .

Keywords : The Quadrature of Electromagnetic Fields in Dual - Photon .

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A).. FROM PRIOR .

1.a. IN Vibrating-Mechanism , masses carry motion as , **Eigenvectors** , at the equilibrium

Positions , which are the **Eigenvectors** , at the Still-Positions . the Orthogonal Property of Normal-Modes for **Eigenvalues** and **Eigenvectors Moulds** is the Process of Equilibrium , to the **2-Half-Area** Still-Positions as Fig-2- , $\pi.[OC]^2 \Rightarrow \pi.[BE]^2 + \pi.[B'E']^2$. and

$$\rightarrow [Z = \oplus \rightarrow \ominus = D] \equiv \left\{ \uparrow Z + \left[\oplus \frac{::}{2} + \ominus \frac{::}{2} \right] D \right\} \equiv \left\{ \pm [\times] \frac{-\oplus/2}{+\ominus/2} + \downarrow \leftrightarrow \uparrow \right\} \leftarrow$$

→ **The Light-Velocity \bar{c} of Photons** , becoming from the **Action** of G on Planck's Length

when act on a-cave , $r = \frac{h}{cZ_c} \neq L_p$ then originates the **Hydrogen-cave**. [99] . Energy is

$$E = h f_m , \text{ because Angular-Momentum } \bar{B} = \frac{2L}{\bar{w}} = \frac{2L}{2\pi f} = \left[\frac{2L}{2\pi} \right] \cdot \left[\frac{1}{f} \right] = \frac{\text{Constant}}{2\pi} \left[\frac{1}{f_m} \right] = \text{SPIN [70].}$$

→ **The Central Axial-Ellipsoid and \oplus constituent Rotating through a constant Point O.**

Figure -1- The 3-dimension motion of $[\ominus \cup \cup \oplus]$ in **PNS-Space** is Angular Momentum \bar{B} .

In (1-2) **Material Point KOK** as {The two circles $\ominus \equiv O, [OK]$ and , $\oplus \equiv O, [OK]$ } where Space Point K (+) and Anti-Point K (-) is rotating through Point O , which is the center of Common circle and form material angle $\phi = \phi_A \cdot t = \left(\frac{v_A}{\sqrt{c^2 - v^2}} \right) \cdot t$, **CREATE** the Cardioid Envelope curves generated by the above Vibrating -Velocity-Energy-Geometry-Segment , KOK on K, [OK] , rolling circle . [79] [109]

The rotation of Space Point K (+) and Anti-Point K (-) through Point O defines Angular momentum \bar{B} , so the Position of Spaces , Point K (+) and Point K (-) , and Momentum are simultaneously determined , which is a direct violation of the **Uncertainty Principle** .

Is shown also the Rotation with angular-velocity \bar{w} , 45° to the instaneous material axis $OP \equiv [\oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus]$ of rotation where Point P is the , **Nib** , of Angular-velocity vector \bar{w} , and Sweeps - Out at OP slant height of the Central , **POT-Cone** , with $\bar{w} = \frac{v}{R} = 2\pi f$.

In (3) are shown **Polhode circle PT** , **Herpolhode PT' circle in Plane E** . Polhode-Cone-POT which is rolling on the Fixed- Herpolhode-Cone **POS** , with the constant Centripetal velocity $|\bar{v}| = \frac{\sigma}{2} [1 + \sqrt{5}] \equiv \sigma \Phi$, dependent on the Pressure , σ , of the two material

constituents $[\oplus, \ominus]$. Photons motion exists on their **Polhode** and **Herpolhode two conjugate circles**. The Integrated Equations of motion become Not from the Center of mass K_0 (Fig-1-) **But** from the center O . Since motion of \oplus constituent becomes from Stress, σ , only, then the constant coordinate System is taken at O , with, z' , axis Perpendicular to the Unit-vector \bar{k} , $[z' \perp \bar{k}]$ which is on OK_0 axis, (is the x axis).

Conclusion-3,

In PNS-Space, Momentum \bar{B} is created from the Eternal Rotation of the two Opposite constituents $[\oplus, \ominus]$ with the constant Centripetal velocity $|\bar{v}| \equiv \sigma \cdot \Phi$, **where the Curl of the velocity vector field** is with the ON-Axis Torque $\nabla \bar{v}$, where $\dot{x} = 0, \dot{y} = 0, \dot{z} = 0$.

In PNS-Space, time exists only as **Period T** from the Rotating constituents $[\oplus, \ominus]$.

B... THE EXTREAMA METHOD OF SQUARING THE CIRCLE.

A Procedure method of, 2-Vectors 3-Poles Rotating Squares Mechanism :

Figure-2- → The Steps for Squaring any circle [O,OA] or (E, EA = EC = EO) on diameter CA through The Sliding of **Point B** on BA arc of circle. From the Four Poles, O, A, C, P, are created on circles [E, EC], [E', E'C], SQUARES, Beginning from CBAO at Point B, CMNH at Point M, CMNH equal to the circle at Point R, and CAC'P at Point A which is Double that of the CBAO. **Simultaneously** the Inscribed to CBAO square circle [E, EC/ $\sqrt{2}$], Becomes greater at Point M, N, and Equal to the circle at Point A.

In (1) is the ARCHEMIDES Expanding method, of the Inscribed circle [O,O1] → to circle [O, OM] and to the circumscribed [O, OA] ..

In (2) is the 2-Vectors 3-Poles Rotating Squares Mechanism, on where all the produced Squares are all Adjustable from the three Poles. There is only one Point R such that forms the Square CMNH equal to the circle.

It is shown Fig-3- that when **SPIN** of Photons = $\frac{1}{2}$, is on **B** Point of this Mechanism, then the Energy of the Conjugate circle is the **Electromagnetic Wave** Producing the Photons motion.

1.B. The Ancient GREEK - SPECIAL - PROBLEMS . [44-50-51- 62]

THE SQUARING OF THE CIRCLE USING THE 2-VECTORS 3-POLES MECHANISM.

Figure -3- The Steps for Squaring any circle on any Two Equal and Perpendicular Vectors CA , CP as Diameters or the circles (E , EC =EA= EO= EB) , (E' , E'C =E'P= E'B'= E'0) , through *The Geometric Requirements* using only a *Compass and a Straightedge* ,with the 2-Vectors , 3-Poles Rotating Squares Mechanism .

When the SPIN $\equiv \vec{B}$ of Photons is on this Mechanism , then **Polhode** is the Circle [B, BE] and **Herpolhode** is the circle [O,OA] , where on it the Energy \equiv Curl-motion $\equiv \vec{c} . 2\pi . [EC]^2$.

- a)... The equal CA , CP Vectors , where CA ⊥ CP and CA = CP
- b)... The equal circles , [E , $\frac{CA}{2} = EC = EA$] . [E' , $\frac{CP}{2} = E'C = E'P$] .

2.B = THE GEOMETRICAL WAY OF THE QUADRAEURE :

THE - STEPS :

- 1.. Draw Straight line Segment , CA as diameter , and let E be the center of the circle (E , EC = EA) .
- 2.. Draw Straight line Segment , CP \perp CA , and as diameter , let E' be the center of the circle (E' , E'C = E'P) .
- 3.. From mid-Point O , of the Hypotynuse AP as center , Draw the circle (O , OA=OP=OC) and Complete the Squares , OCBA , OCB'P .
On Perpendicular diameters OB , OB' and from Points B , B' draw *The Conjugate circles* , (B, BE=EC) , (B' , B'E'=E'C) rerspectively , intersecting the (E, EC) , (E' , OP) circles at Points [R , R'] respectively,
- 4.. Draw on the diameter COC' the Perpendicular RG , such that $RG \perp CC'$.
- 5.. From Point P Draw a Parallel to AG line , intersecting CC' at Point G' , and the circles (O , OA) , (E' , E'P) at Points N - H , respectively.
- 6.. Draw the line NA so that its extension intersects the circle (E , EA) at Point M and draw Segments CM , CH and Complete Quatrilateral CMNH , [*which is a Square* , calling it , *The Space = The Circles-System*] .
Draw the line NP so that its extension intersects the circle (E' , E'P) at Point N' and draw Segments CM' , CH' and Complete Quatrilateral CM'N'H' , [*which is also Square calling it , The Anti - Space = The-Idol = The Anti - System*] .
- 7.. Complete Quatrilateral CAC'P , [*which is a Square*] ,
- 8.. Show that Quadrilaterals CMNH , CM'N'H' are Squares , and that
 $CMNH = [CM]^2 = \pi.[EC]^2$ & $CM'N'H' = [CM']^2 = \pi.[EC]^2$

Analysis :

- a...Point M on circle (E , EC) forms the Right angle \widehat{CMA} , because lies on diameter CA .
- b...Point N on circle (O , OA) forms the Right angle \widehat{MNP} , because lies on diameter AP .
- c...Point H on circle (E' , E'C) forms the Right angle \widehat{CHP} , because lies on diameter CP .
and because angle $\widehat{CHP} = 180^\circ - 90^\circ = 90^\circ$, then angle $\widehat{CHN} = 90^\circ$
- d...Point C on circle (O,OC) forms the Right angle \widehat{MCH} , because $\widehat{MCH} = 360^\circ - 270^\circ = 90^\circ$
therefore Quadrilateral CMNH is an Orthogonal-Quadrilateral . Since also issues the line $AG \parallel PN$ and $GO \perp AP$ then the alternate interior angles are equal and , $\mathbf{OG = OG'}$.
Since the Right-angles triangles CAM - CPH have their sides CA , CP, equal and the two Angles \widehat{CMA} , \widehat{CPH} equal each other **therefore** are Equal and Sides $CM = CH$, and since **Quadrilateral CMNH is an Orthogonal-Quadrilateral with Equal Sides it is SQUARE.**

Conclusions :

- 1...Any Point M on (E, EC) circle , arc between the Points B , A , forms the Square , CMNH on *The Circles - System* , and the Square , CM'N'H' , on **The-Idol \rightarrow The Anti - System** .
Since squares CBAO , CAC'P , belong to the circles (E, EC) , (O,OC = OA) , therefore

This Mechanism carries the Area $\pi.[EC]^2$ of (E, EC) circle, to circle (O, OC = OA). Since the inscribed circle to Square CAC'P is equal to the circle (E, EC), therefore this Mechanism carries all Properties of the circle from Point B to A.

Since also square CAC'P = 2 . CBAO, then $\pi.[OC]^2 = 2. \pi.[EC]^2$. **i.e. The Mechanism carries circle (E, EC) to circle (O, OC = OA) of Double Area.**

2...The Circles Anti-circles System are Equal and Placed Symmetrical on common axis.

3...The Rolling of Point M on (E, EC) circle means \rightarrow Radius of Curvature $ME \perp MT \leftarrow \tan$

3.B = THE GEOMETRICAL LOGIC & PROOF :

1.. It was Proved [44] and from Analysis, that when Point B is Rolling on the circumference of circle (E, EC) – [say **Point M**] and MA line extended at Point N of circle (O, OC = OA) by Joining PN which intersects the circle (E', E'C) at Point H, **Then** the formed Square CMNH is in the circle (O, OC = OA).

2.. When Point M is **on Point B**, common to circle (E, EC) and to center of circle (B, BE), BA line extended at Point A of circle (O, OC = OA) and Joining PA and intersecting the circle (E', E'C) at Point O, the formed square CBAO is the square in circle (E, EC).

Since the Conjugate circle (B, BE) is constant and Unmovable and the Only motion is the Rotational-motion, Therefore This circle (B, BE) carries the Properties of this circle say the Area of circle $\pi.[EB]^2$ in the circle (E, EC) and issues $\pi.[EB]^2 = \pi.[EC]^2$

3.. When Point M is **on Point R**, common to circles (E, EC), (B, BE), **Then** $C R N_R H_R$ is also a Square in the circle (O, OC = OA). This **Conjugate circle** carries the Properties of circle (B, BE) say, **The Inscribed Square CBAO** which is equal to that of circle and the **Area of circle = $\pi.[EC]^2$** in the circle (O, OC = OA), **But How ? \Rightarrow In-Reverse.**

To Show that at Point R, , Common to circles (E, EC), (B, BE), ,

The Conjugate circle (B, BE), Stores its Properties to the Half circle (O, OC = OA).

Since OB is diameter in circle (E, EO) and angle $\widehat{BRO} = 90^\circ$, **therefore** $RB \perp RO$. At this Point R the Radius of Curvature **RB, is Perpendicular to AT-tangent \rightarrow RO** and Passes from Point O. Since Geometrical-Vector **RO** is analysed to $RG \perp CC'$ and $GO \parallel CC'$ then is formed the Symmetrical Point R' on circle (E', E'C) and Point G', where $OG = OG'$. By Extending PG' on circles (E', E'C), (O, OC = OA), by occupying H, N Points and Extending NA to M Point on (E, EC) circle **then CMNH is Square . i.e.**

The area of circle (B, BE) \equiv (E, EC), is Transported to the Half of circle (O, OC), and

$$\pi . [EC]^2 \equiv CMNH = [CM]^2 \quad \& \quad \pi \equiv \frac{CMNH}{(EC)^2} \quad \dots\dots\dots \text{o.e.d.}$$

4.. When Point M is **on Point A**, common to circles (E, EC), (O, OC), **Then** CAC'P is also a Square in the circle (O, OC = OA). **At this Point A** the Radius of Curvature **AE, is Perpendicular (\perp) to AT-tangent \rightarrow AC', which Passes from Point C', i.e.**

The area of circle (B, BE) \equiv (E, EC), is Transported to the Halve circle (O, OC).

4.B = THE MECHANICAL LOGIC & PROOF :

- 1.. It was Proved [44] and from Analysis that on the **2-Vectors , 3-Poles Rotating Squares Mechanism**, when a Point **M** on arc **BA** is Rolling on the circumference of circle (E,EC) and MA line extended at Point **N** of circle (O,OC= OA) by Joining PN , which intersects the circle |E',E'C| at Point **H** , **Then** the formed **Square CMNH** is in circle |O,OC= OA| **When SPIN** $\equiv \vec{B}$ of **Photons** is on this **Mechanism** at the constant Point **B** , then **Polhode** is the Circle [B , BE] and **Herpolhode** is the circle [O , OA] , where on B Point motion is only the SPIN $\equiv \vec{B} \equiv \bar{c} \cdot \pi \cdot [EC]^2$. This Quantity of Energy in **Polhode** is Stored in the [O ,OA] Half circle of the **Total Energy** \equiv The Curl-motion $\equiv \bar{c} \cdot 2\pi \cdot [EC]^2$.
- 2..The Rolling of Point **B** on (E, EC) circle means \rightarrow Radius of Curvature **BE** \perp **BA** \leftarrow tang. where \vec{C}_C, \vec{C}_T , are the two constitues of light velocity vector \bar{c} . i.e. $\bar{c} = \vec{B} / \pi \cdot [EC]^2$. When Spin \vec{B} is on Point B , common to circle (E, EC) and at the center of circle (B, BE) BA line extended at Point A of circle (O,OC= OA) and Joining PA intersects the circle (E', E'C) at Point O , then the formed square CBAO , is the square in circle (E , EC). **Since the Conjugate circle** (B , BE) is constant and Unmovable and the Only motion is the Rotational-motion SPIN $\equiv \vec{B} \equiv \bar{c} \cdot \pi \cdot [EC]^2$., **Therefore The circle** (B , BE) carries the motion $\bar{c} \cdot \pi \cdot [EB]^2$ in the circle (E , EC) , where from relation $|\vec{C}_H| \equiv \sigma \cdot \Phi$ on AB and from relation $|\vec{C}_V| \equiv \sigma \cdot \Phi$ on CO squares , issues $\Rightarrow \bar{c} \cdot \pi \cdot [EC]^2 \equiv \bar{c} \cdot \pi \cdot [EB]^2$,
- 3..Since motion is in circle (E , EC) , the Tangential velocity $\vec{C}_T = \bar{c}$ Passes from Point O , since angle BGO = 90° on diameter OB . At Point G , the **Velocity** \bar{c} is analyzed to the Horizontal and Vertical velocities \vec{C}_H, \vec{C}_V , The Horizontal velocity vector $\vec{GO}_H = \vec{OG}'_H$ carries Energy into NCMH=CMNH Square which Area is the carried Energy= $\bar{c} \cdot \pi \cdot [EC]^2$ The vector \vec{OG}'_H , continuously acting on Point G' carries Energy in Point C' of Square C'ECA = 2.CBAO and the Area $\bar{c} \cdot \pi \cdot [OA]^2 \equiv \bar{c} \cdot 2\pi \cdot [EC]^2$.
- 4..The vector \vec{RG}_V , continuously acting on Axis CO' carries Energy on the Symmetrical Square COPB'. The vector \vec{OG}'_H , continuously acting on Point G carries Energy in the Point C of Anti-Square CM'N'O = 2.CB'A'P and of Area $\bar{c} \cdot \pi \cdot [OP]^2 \equiv \bar{c} \cdot 2\pi \cdot [E'C]^2$.
- 5..With above Motion , Photon carries the **Polhode Energy** = $\bar{c} \cdot \pi \cdot [EC]^2$ into **Herpolhode Half-Circle Energy Store** , and into the **Anti-Herpolhode Half-Circle Energy Store** also. **The vector \vec{OG}'_H by carrying Energy on axis CC' , creates the motion of Mechanism**
The Energy in **Polhode** = $\bar{c} \cdot \pi \cdot [EC]^2$ circle , constitutes the **Electric – Field E , of the Electromagnetic Waves E ,M .**
The Energy in **Anti-Polhode** = $\bar{c} \cdot \pi \cdot [E'C]^2$ circle , constitutes the **Magnetic – Field M , of the Electromagnetic Waves E ,M . and thus**
Photon Electromagnetic - Waves , **E** \perp **M** , travel in all Spaces and affected by the Gravitational force **G** only .

C.. THE ELECTRON AND PHOTON CHARGES :

Figure 4. Conservation of motion ≡ Energy in the Primary-Material-Point-Field-lines :

$$\text{Photon} \equiv \text{Energy} \equiv \text{motion} / T \equiv \left(\frac{v}{2\pi r}\right) \cdot [\sigma + \sigma \Phi] = \vec{v} \cdot \left[\frac{\sigma}{2\pi r} + \frac{\sigma\Phi}{2\pi r}\right] \equiv \vec{v} \cdot \left[\vec{f}_n\right] + f_n \equiv$$

$$\text{Moving - Storage} \rightarrow [\vec{v} \cdot \vec{f}_n] \leftarrow + \text{Moving-Frequency} \rightarrow [\vec{v} \cdot f_n] \leftarrow \equiv \text{Material-Point i.e.}$$

The Energy Produced in Photon-Cave is consisted of **Two-moving-Storages**, which travel. The Stationary-Charged-Particle is from equation, $g \cdot f^2 \cdot \pi^3 = 1$, where π is the Closed Space, πg is the Stationary-Electric-Lines, and $f_1 = \sqrt{g^{-1}\pi^{-3}}$, the motion = Energy = **the Stress** in the Two and Opposite-Spaces, [{+} → {-}], or in the consisted Poles, with Infinite Points and Parallel-lines such as **G** which is as An - Uniform-Pointy-Force. Electrons can be Spinning clockwise or anti-clockwise and Propagate on a Spiral trajectory. A true definition of what is Electric-Charge and Electricity based on above follows.

In [1] The-Stationary-Electron-Charge

$$\text{Becomes from E - equation } \bar{q} \equiv \frac{m_e c^2}{2} = \frac{g}{4\pi f^2 e} \left[\frac{c^2}{2}\right] = \frac{g c^2}{8\pi f^2}$$

while for Photon is directly from $G = F = \sigma A = (2\pi f r) \frac{A}{\Phi} = w r \frac{A}{\Phi} = \vec{v} \frac{A}{\Phi} = \sigma \Phi^3$, which is a straight-line-Voltage. Since Energy is Produced from motion, which is the continuous removal of [{+} to →{-}] and because it occurs in Closed-loops, *The Electric-Field-lines are Straight-lines, in Space Φ and Energy-Field σ* and when these Pass from **g** ocean then continue to be *Straight-lines*, and this because Total-work $W = F \cdot s = [F \perp s] = 0 = h f = 0$.

The Geometry of cave (Tack-Geometry) controls the Electric-field and the Stability from **g** while equilibrium from, $g f^2 \pi^3 = 1$, and created from the two opposite Angular Momentum vectors, M_u, M_d , at distance, r , and thus is created the **E-Spin** as $2S = M_u \times \{ \{+ \} \rightarrow \{- \} \}$, and is acting on [{+} → {-}] axis. **i.e.**

The Stationary- Electron - Charge is the Storage of $r \equiv L_p$, cave in-where the *Space* and *Anti-space*, as πg , and as Stationary-Electric-Lines are creating Potential-Energy P_E , with such Geometry that, to exist from the linear-motion are stored in the form of **Dipole-Rotation with a changing-Spin, S, and of frequency $f = 1/T$ in the min-cave**. Here is cleared that frequency $f_e = B/(\pi^2 r^4)$ of Electron is Energy as angular velocity vector motion in r cave, and this is because in cave exists the **Natural-Frequency $f_n = \sqrt{g^{-1}\pi^{-3}}$** of cave in Electric-Field-lines $E = g \pi$. Photon Frequency becomes from the

Isochronous motion $w = \frac{2\pi}{T} = \frac{g}{4r} = 2\pi f$ which **Amplitude is Independent of motion**, and its velocity $\bar{v} = [\frac{G\Phi}{A}]$, is **Dependent on Impedance Z_p** of Space-Anti Space A.

In [2] the Electrostatic Unit of Charge \bar{q}_p , the Quantum of All, which when concentrated at Point $\{+\}$ and placed at a unit distance from an equal and Opposite concentrated quantity $\{-\}$ **Is the Pulling with a Unit - force**. Mass m_e is the reaction to this Inner motion of $\{+\} \rightarrow \{-\}$ and consists the **Granular- Storage of Energy motion**, which is vibration in a closed loop, and it is a measurable Physical-quantity denoting the Geometry of Electron in r cave, and Periodic motion. The Geometry of the Periodic motion issues the same such as for and for Material Point with different cave and one-frequency as equation

$$f_e = \frac{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma}{4\pi r} = \frac{\sigma\Phi}{2\pi r} = \frac{\bar{B}}{\pi^2 \cdot r^4}$$

Electric-current is then The flow of the Electric-Charges and which is the moving-quantity of Charges. Since *Electrons* and *Electric Charges* exists in, **$g \pi$ loop-level**, therefore IS the Property that controls all interactions between Bodies through these **Electrical-forces**.

In [2] The-Stationary-Photon-Charge is the case of Material Point with **Periodic Orbital motion** where issues the **Tack-Geometry** i.e. the tracks of the Electric-lines Pattern are closed loops and not straight-lines, and also because of the Voltage between the ends, is created the motion as an *Eternal rotation* of the $[\oplus]$ constituent towards $[\ominus]$ constituent, [The opposite issues for Rotational motion where in the *Moving-Photon-Tank* and because of Stress, σ , is created the Centrifugal-Force F_f]. and $\bar{v} = [\frac{G\Phi}{A}]$.

Because $f_n = \frac{\bar{B}}{\pi^2 \cdot r^4} = \frac{\sigma^2 \cdot \Phi^2}{4 \cdot \bar{B}}$ so, the Stress $\sigma = 0 \rightarrow \sigma$, and $\bar{B} = \text{Angular-Momentum} = \text{AM}$ independent of $\sigma \rightarrow \text{AM}$, and Spin is equal to $\text{AM} / \text{Unit-Area} = \text{AM} / \pi$, and because of the Closed *One-way loops*,

Spin is either Positive or Negative and it is $\rightarrow \text{Electric-Charge } \bar{E} = \pm \text{AM} / \pi = \text{E-Spin} = \text{The } \pm \text{ Electron}$. Above Spin disappears the ERP Paradox because is extended and actually is filling up the entire universe. These Stationary-Particles are permanently entangled, with Wave packets becoming from M-P-Photons, which Orientate and Re-orientate their Spins.

In [3] the The-Moving-Photon-Charge Is consisted of the above **Energy-Storage**, the g in **min-cave**, occupying *All Properties of the Stationary-Electron-Charge* and **additionally** the Kinetic-energy $E = \frac{m_e v^2}{2} = g \cdot v_e^2 / 8\pi f_e^2 = \bar{q}_e V = h \cdot f_e$, and $g \cdot v_e^2 = 8\pi h \cdot f_e^3$, or $[v_e^2 / f_e^3] = 8\pi h / g = \text{constant}$, or $v_e^2 / f_e^3 = k$, and $v_e^2 \cdot T_e^3 = k = \frac{f^3}{f^3} = f^3 \left(\frac{T}{\lambda}\right)^2 = f^3 \cdot \left[\frac{1}{\lambda f}\right]^2 = k$, the Kepler unit of time i.e. The *Electron-velocity squared* to the *Electron`s - cube Frequency* is constant following the Orbit-Unit-Energy equation $k = f^2_e a^3$, and equal to the Inverse f squared to the *Electron`s-cube Frequency* in wavelength λ interchanged and

keeping light-velocity \bar{c} without any other Force acting on them .

This Kinetic-Energy creates Angular velocity $\omega = 2E/B = \frac{m_e v^2}{B}$ and the Inwards transverse

Electromagnetic-Waves , $E \perp M$, travelling with v_e , inner velocity as

$E = A \cdot \sin[kx - \omega t]$ and as $M = A \cdot \sin[kx - \omega t]$, and $E = M = A \cdot [1 - \sin \omega t]$, since $\sin kx = 0$.

i.e. The Moving-Electron-Charge is The Electromagnetic-Wave , $E \perp M$, which carries the Stationary-Electron-Charge, and which is The STORAGE of g , in min-cave inwhere the Potential-Energy P_E , as linear-motion in $g \equiv r$ cave is stored in the form of Dipole rotation , *Angular-momentum due to curved motion* , with Spin , S , is directed from $\{-\} \rightarrow \{+\}$ and to G - Primary-Direction of frequency $f = 1/T$, and which is the Source in cave r .

The Kepler Unit of time $k = f^2_e a^3$ where $a = \lambda/2$, consists the Clock in Nature and Measures the changes of motions .

1.C..Application to the Photon Gravitational bending : $\begin{matrix} 2 \times d \rightarrow & \downarrow & 4 \times d \rightarrow \\ & S & \leftrightarrow \end{matrix}$

From [39] Monads , as an **Electromagnetic Standing wave move in Field [MFMF] =**

$= s^2 = \pm |(wr)^2|$ as *the smallest Quantized Space of this level* . Let ,

$L =$ The length of an undergoing constant acceleration monad in **Gravity field** ,

$t = L/c \rightarrow$ is the needed **Time** to cross the length L ,

$s = at^2/2 = aL^2/2c^2 \rightarrow$ is the **Deflection** due to acceleration , a ,

1.. For a monad in Planck's length 10^{-35} m then time $T = 8,906.10^{-35}/3.10^8 = 2,968.10^{-43}$ s and , the Deflection $s = aT^2/2 = 9,81.8,809.10^{-70} = 4,320836.10^{-85}$ m

2.. The Photon velocity vector \vec{v}_{ph} , when passes by the Sun's surface changes direction . This Phenomenon is caused from the Gravitational force between Photon and Sun. Since velocity vector changes direction this means acceleration , therefore use Newton formula $F = m_{ph} \cdot a$. Since the Force-vector is applied Perpendicularly to the **initial velocity vector** , therefore the **Centripetal Force** causes the velocity-vector rotation which is Newton's Gravitational force F ,

$$F = G \cdot \frac{M_{sun} \cdot m_{ph}}{d_1^2} = \frac{6,673.10^{-11} Nm^2/Kg^2 \cdot [1,989.10^{30} Kg] \cdot [8,84655.10^{-21} Kg]}{[691.10^6]^2} = 2,4590861.10^{-18} N \dots (1P)$$

$$F = G \cdot \frac{M_{sun} \cdot m_{ph}}{d_2^2} = \frac{6,673.10^{-11} Nm^2/Kg^2 \cdot [1,989.10^{30} Kg] \cdot [8,84655.10^{-21} Kg]}{[4x6,91.10^8]^2} = 0,1532489.10^{-18} N$$

where , the mass of the Sun $M_{sun} = 1989.10^{30}$ Kg , of Photon $m_{ph} = 8,846562.10^{-21}$ Kg.

$d =$ the distance between the two centers of mass = Sun's Radius = 691.10^6 m . Because the component velocity v_{\perp} , is Perpendicular to \vec{c} velocity vector and force F constant , so

exists acceleration according to Newton's equation $F = m_{ph} \cdot a$.

Acceleration $a = [\frac{F}{m_{ph}}] = \frac{2,459.10^{-18} N}{8,846562.10^{-21} Kg} = 277,96108 \text{ m/s}^2 \dots (2P)$, and $a = 1,73229 \text{ m/s}^2$.

The component velocity $v_{\perp} = a \cdot t$ where t is the time needed Photon's vector to run the Sun's diameter as $\rightarrow t = n \cdot d_s / c = n \cdot [13,82.10^8/2,997.10^8] = 4,6112779 \times n \approx 9,22$ s . for a Cone of

2 diameters , and Change of Velocity $\Delta v_{1\perp} = 277,96108 \cdot 9,22 = 2562,8011 \text{ m/s} \dots (3P)$. For $n = 4$

$t = 18,22$ s and $\Delta v_{2\perp} = 1,73229 \cdot 18,22 = 31,56232 \text{ m/s}$ and $w_{2,arc.sec} = 0,21715144 \text{ arcsec}$

Because the vector v_{\perp} is perpendicular to \bar{c} vector, therefore for angle w , $\tan w = [\frac{\Delta v_{\perp}}{c}]$ and

$w_{1,rad} = \arctan\{\frac{2562,8011 \text{ m/s}}{2,998.10^8 \text{ m/s}}\} = 8,5512215.10^{-6}$ radians . Since $1 \text{ rad} = [\frac{180}{\pi} \times 3600]$ then ,

$w_{1,arc.sec} = 8,5512215.10^{-6} \times [\frac{180}{\pi} \times 3600] = 1,7638159 \text{ arcsec} \dots (4P)$

2.C.The Photon Gravitational–Bending is NOT Lensing of Spacetime, [Milky-Way Star]

DATA :

$G = 6,673.10^{-11} \text{ Nm}^2/\text{Kg}^2$. → Newton`s Gravitational constant ,

$\vec{c} = 2,998.10^8 \text{ m/s}$, The Photon`s velocity vector ,

$m_{\text{ph}} = 8,846562.10^{-21} \text{ Kg}$, → The mass (Reaction to motion) of Photon .

$M_{\text{GAL}} = 0,8 .10^{30} \text{ Kg}$, → The mass of Galaxy ,

$r_{\text{GAL}} = 0,8 .10^9 \text{ m}$, The radius of Galaxy ,

$d_{\text{GAL}} = 1,6 .10^9 \text{ m}$, The diameter of the Galaxy.

$r_{\text{G-P}} = 1,6 .10^9 \text{ m}$, The distance between Galaxy – Photon .

a)..From Newton`s , Law of Universal Gravitation , the attraction force F is as ,

$$F = G \cdot \frac{M_{\text{GAL}} \cdot m_{\text{ph}}}{r_{\text{G-P}}^2} = \frac{6,673.10^{-11} \text{ Nm}^2/\text{Kg}^2 \cdot [0,8.10^{30} \text{ Kg}] \cdot [8,84655.10^{-21} \text{ Kg}]}{[1,6.10^9 \text{ m}]^2} = 1,844782.10^{-19} \text{ N} , \dots(1G)$$

b)..Because the component velocity v_{\perp} , is Perpendicular to \vec{c} velocity vector and the force F is constant , so exists acceleration according to the 2nd Newton`s law → $F = m_{\text{ph}} \cdot a$.

$$\text{Acceleration } a = \left[\frac{F}{m_{\text{ph}}} \right] = \frac{1,844782.10^{-19} \text{ N}}{8,846562.10^{-21} \text{ Kg}} = 20,853095 \text{ m/s}^2 \dots(2G)$$

c).The component velocity $v_{\perp} = a \cdot t$ where , t , is the time needed by the Photon`s vector to run the Sun`s diameter in Cone of $n = 2$ -diameter as distance as equation → $t = n \cdot d_{\text{S}} / c$, and , $t = 2 \cdot [1,6 .10^9 / 2,998.10^8] = 2 \times 5,3368912 \approx 10,673782 \text{ s}$. for a Cone of

2 diameters , and Change of Velocity $\Delta v_{2\perp} = a \times t = 20,8531.10,674 = 222,58139 \text{ m/s} \dots(3G)$

d)..Because vector v_{\perp} is perpendicular to \vec{c} vector, therefore for angle w issues $\tan w = \left[\frac{\Delta v_{\perp}}{c} \right]$ as

$$w_{2.\text{rad}} = \arctan \left\{ \frac{222,58139 \text{ m/s}}{2,998.10^8 \text{ m/s}} \right\} = 7,4243292.10^{-7} \text{ radians} . \text{ Since } 1 \text{ rad} = \left[\frac{180}{\pi} \times 3600 \right] \text{ then ,}$$

$$w_{2.\text{arc.sec}} = 7,4243292.10^{-7} \times \left[\frac{180}{\pi} \times 3600 \right] = 0,15313777 \text{ arcsec} \dots\dots(4G)$$

e)..For a distance $4 \times r_{\text{GAL}} = 3,2 .10^9 \text{ m}$ then , $F = G \cdot \frac{M_{\text{GAL}} \cdot m_{\text{ph}}}{r_{\text{G-P}}^2} = 1,152988.10^{-19} \text{ N}$,

$$\text{Acceleration } a = \left[\frac{F}{m_{\text{ph}}} \right] = 1,3033184 \text{ m/s}^2 , \quad t = 4 \cdot d_{\text{S}} / c \approx 21,347564 \text{ s} \dots(5G)$$

$$\Delta v_{4\perp} = a \times t = 27,822672 \text{ m/s} , w_{4.\text{rad}} = 9,280411.10^{-8} \text{ rad} , w_{2.\text{arc.sec}} = 0,01014222 \text{ arcsec} .$$

Remarks :

- 1.. From Photon equation $\Rightarrow \vec{v} \cdot \left[\vec{f}_n + f_n \right] \equiv \left| \frac{v}{\pi^2 \cdot r_n^4} \right| \cdot \left[\vec{B}_n \right] + |\vec{c}| f_n$, and when $c = 0$, motion is $\left| \frac{v}{\pi^2 \cdot r_n^4} \right| \cdot \left[\vec{B}_n \right]$ which is motion in a **Standing wave** . Photon is of Dual nature and is Electromagnetic field .where the **Electric-field Produces** the Work and the **Magnetic - Field Stores** the Work .
From Physics , *mass is the reaction to the motion* which means the meter of the motion .`Newton`s Gravitational force is the dominant force in nature in which subject all **meters of motions** , or masses, **i.e. for Photons , Electric - field is the motion and Magnetic Field is the reaction to this motion , which is thus the mass of Photons** .

When Newton`s third law (Action-Reaction) is applied on Photon-Wave whenever **Electric-field** exerts a Force =Action on **Magnetic - Field** , then the Magnetic - Field exerts an Reaction = Force.

- 2.. **We apply Newton`s second law and Vector - Kinematics , for a duration of the Newton`s Gravitational force , on a Path of the time vector at a distance of 2 – diameters.**
- 3.. The Perpendicular Impulse is as the Centripetal acceleration which causes the motion on the arc and the continuous change of the velocity vector to the direction of the Force .
- 4.. The final velocity vector is the Sum of the Initial Horizontal velocity and the New Vertical component velocity vector , while the New Direction is that of the Resultant of the two vectors .
- 5.. The direction of the Photon's Resultant-velocity is maximum at the Point of contact of the orbiting Sphere, and decreases with the Photon's distance from the center of its Precession orbit.

6.. The Gravitational force between the velocity vector \vec{c} and an Object , IS Proportional to their masses m_c and m_o and Inversely Proportional to the square of their distance d_{co} as $F_G = G \cdot \frac{m_c \cdot m_o}{d_{co}^2}$ (N)

The Centripetal Force F_G Produces a New velocity vector \vec{c}' which is added to \vec{c} vector .**The Resultant velocity vector \vec{v}_R forms the Deflection angle w , to the \vec{c} velocity vector .**

7..The light-rays and consequently the Photons travel in Straight lines .

8..Time is the meter , to measure the changes in , Energy = motion = Force x displacement.

9..The Gravitational force G , causes the Bending of light rays (of Photons) , and **Not the warping** of Spacetime which Time is Not existing , **on the contrary** , **Space-energy**, is the essence of existence..

It was shown in [70-P32] that in a Cycloid , the area between the curve and the straight line is $A = 3\pi r^2$ and the arc length $l = 8r$. For the motion on cycloid , we consider a **Weight Q** , at a point A , moving with free motion . Since reaction N , is vertically acting , Q , so doesn't give any Tangential component , and the only one becomes from Q , which is equal to $AT = g \cdot \sin \varphi$ and since $\sin \varphi = \frac{s}{4r}$

then issues $AT = g \cdot \frac{s}{4r}$. Since acceleration $a = \frac{d^2s}{dt^2} = \frac{dv}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt}(\frac{ds}{dt}) = \{-g \cdot \frac{s}{4r}\}$ then $\frac{d^2s}{dt^2} = -g \cdot \frac{s}{4r}$ or

$\{\ddot{s} = -w^2 \dot{s} \text{ where } w = \frac{2\pi}{T} = \frac{g}{4r}\}$... (a) and is a **Harmonic Oscillatory motion** showing that Acceleration

is Proportional to displacement and is directed towards the origin with a Period $T = \frac{2\pi}{w} = 2\pi \cdot \sqrt{\frac{4r}{g}} =$

$4\pi \cdot \sqrt{\frac{r}{g}}$, or and $w^2 = [\frac{g}{4r}]^2$, **where** $w = 2\pi f = \frac{g}{4r}$. From Total-Energy $2L = J \cdot w^2 = 4\pi^2 \cdot f^2$, the Circular

frequency is $w^2 = \frac{(\sigma\Phi)^2}{r^2} = [2\pi f]^2$, and the Cycloidal-Frequency $f_p = |\frac{\sigma\Phi}{2\pi r}| = \frac{[1+\sqrt{5}]\sigma}{4\pi r} = \frac{\sigma\Phi}{2\pi r}$... (f)

Equation (f) relates , Circular frequency w , frequency f_p , Stress σ , in any cave , r , **from a Force Q**

in a free motion . In the case of Photon , the Gravitational-Constant-Force G , becomes as Stress \equiv

Force / Area $\equiv g$, as equation $G = gk_E = g \cdot [g_E k_E] = [\frac{T^2 P}{a^3}] \cdot [g_L k_L] = [\frac{c \cdot r^3}{a^3}] \cdot [g_L k_L] = 9,8076925 * [..]$

$6,8116 \cdot 10^{-12} = 6,68056 \cdot 10^{-11} \frac{m^3}{Ns^2}$, and **Effects on gravity** $\rightarrow g \equiv 9,8076925$ Stress $\frac{Kg}{cm^2}$ [73]

The Beyond-Planck-length Force $F = \sigma \cdot A =$ The Glue-Bond \equiv Stress x Area $\equiv [\frac{2\pi f \cdot r}{\Phi}] \cdot A = w r \cdot [\frac{A}{\Phi}] =$

$\bar{v} [\frac{A}{\Phi}]$ and becomes a moving Storage $\frac{A}{\Phi}$ travelling with velocity \bar{v} , n times that of light-velocity c , as equation $\bar{v} = n c$. [77]

3.C..The Greatest Energy Pressure-Level : From [89] .

The explanation of Pascal's -Triangle in M-Geometry and *Application In Jericho Walls*,

Figure – 5 : The [+] Spaces , [-] Anti-Spaces , [+ -] Sub-Spaces in a circle (R , OA)
The Material-Geometry explanation of Pascal's - Triangle

Stress $\sigma = \frac{\text{Force}}{\text{Area}}$, and is the Pressure executed by the Force on Surface A . Sound Pressure SP, is the Pressure measured within the wave relative to the surrounding air Pressure.

The SP , like other kinds of Pressure ,is commonly measured in units of Pascal's (Pa) $= \frac{\text{N}}{\text{m}^2} = \frac{\text{Kg}}{\text{ms}^2} = \frac{\text{J}}{\text{m}^3}$, with minimum SP ,equal to Quantum $p_0 = 2.10^{-5} \text{ Pa} \equiv 0 \text{ (dB)}$ the Decibel .

The equation of Sound-Pressure-Level ,SPL, is $L_{SP} = 20.\log_{10}(\frac{P}{P_0}) \text{ dB}$,where P =Pressure $L_{SP0} = 0 \text{ dB}$ corresponds at frequency $f_s = 1 \text{ kHz} = 1000 \text{ Hz}$. The Sound-Intensity-Level , SIL0 is , $L_{SI} = 10.\log_{10}(\frac{I}{I_0}) \text{ dB}$, where Intensity $I = \frac{P^2}{Z_0}$ and Impedance $Z_0 = 400 \text{ Ns/m}^3$ The greatest SP, cannot be exceeded the average air pressure which is 101325 Pa and fixed

$$\text{SPL , is } L_{SP} = 20.\log_{10}(\frac{101325}{0,00002}) = 194 \text{ dB} \dots\dots(s1)$$

In Material Geometry Photon-frequency $f_{ph} = [\frac{\sigma}{2\pi r} + \frac{\sigma\Phi}{2\pi r}]$ which is related to the Stress ,

$\sigma = \text{Force/Area}$, and is the **Energy-Pressure-Level , EPL** , of the **Wave + Particle Photon** , for its frequency .The Greatest EPL for the two Opposite-Elements $\{\oplus , \ominus\}$ in Space is their Permutation $P_{IS}^2 = 2$ and for Anti-Space $P_{IAS}^2 = 2$ or for both $P_{I,S+A}^2 = 2 \cdot 2 = 4$ min-Levels .

Because [9] , The Circumscribed-Regular-Polygons in a circle (R,OA) Denote the Spaces and Anti-Spaces $[(\oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus)]$, and Inscribed-Regular-Polygons of the circle Denote the Sub-Spaces **and Because** [63] ,The Regular-Polygons Denote the Structure of Material-Geometry to be as A Point $\rightarrow n = 1 \quad m = 2 , \{ S \equiv \oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus \equiv A \} \rightarrow S = \text{Space} , A = \text{Anti-Space}$

Line-sector $\rightarrow n = 2 , m = 4 , \begin{pmatrix} S & \leftrightarrow & S \\ S & \rightarrow & A \\ A & \leftrightarrow & A \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow S = \text{Space} , A = \text{Anti-Space}$

Plane-Triangle $\rightarrow n = 3 , m = 6 , \begin{pmatrix} S & A & S \\ s & s & s \\ A & S & A \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow S = \text{Space} , A = \text{Anti-Space} \quad s = \text{Sub-Space}$

A Volume $\rightarrow n = 4 , m = 8 , \begin{pmatrix} S & A & S \\ s & S & s \\ A & S & A \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow S = \text{Space} , A = \text{Anti-Space} \quad s = \text{Sub-Space}$

and Because Regular-Hexagon is of $3 \times 2 = 6$ Vertices on **Plane-Triangle** +

Regular--Octagon is of $4 \times 2 = 8$ Vertices on **Volume-Tetrahedron** then ,

Regular-Heptagon-Anti Heptagon is of , $7 \times 2 = 14$ Vertices [63-P70].

Regular-Heptagon Between the Two-Regions , **Plane -Volume** , Needs more **Pressure** ,and consists the Upper - Largest Energy-Level with Permutation , the number of **Permutation** with Repetition of the **Seventh** - Element as , $RP_n^n \equiv n^2 \rightarrow P_7^7 = 7^2 = 49$, and

The Greatest **EPL** is $\rightarrow P_{I,S+A}^2 \times P_7^7 = 4 \times 49 = 196 = L_{EP} = 196 \text{ dB} \dots(s2)$

Remarks :

- 1... The Stress σ is executed on all Surfaces , either in Planes or on Surfaces of Volumes , and consists the exclusive-meter of measurements , in dB , in all nature .
- 2... Stress σ , occupies minimum and maximum limits , $0 \approx 196 \text{ dB}$,differing 2 Units which

can be changed by altering the Base of Pressure from 101325 \rightarrow 102389 Pa .

3... Minimum and Maximum limits , $0 \approx 194 \approx 196$ dB , become from $L_{EP} = \left[\frac{\pi^2}{Nc} \right]^3 = 194$ dB

4... Stress σ , occupies Minimum and Maximum because is related to frequency and velocity

$$f_{ph} = \left[\frac{\sigma}{2\pi r} + \frac{\sigma\Phi}{2\pi r} \right] \equiv \frac{\sigma + \sigma\Phi}{2\pi r} = \frac{\sigma[1+\Phi]}{2\pi r} = \frac{\sigma[\Phi]^2}{2\pi r}, \text{ or } \sigma \equiv \frac{f_{ph} \cdot 2\pi \cdot r}{\Phi^2} \equiv \frac{w \cdot r}{\Phi^2} \equiv \frac{v}{\Phi^2} \equiv \bar{c} \frac{1}{\Phi^2}$$

and is **The-Stress-Way** of Photon-Storages $\boxed{\bar{f}_n} \equiv \frac{\sigma}{2\pi r}$, and Photon-Information $f_n \equiv \frac{\sigma\Phi}{2\pi r}$

From force $G \equiv \sigma \cdot \Phi^3 \equiv \Phi^2 \cdot \{ \sigma \Phi \} \equiv \left[\frac{2B}{\pi r^3} \right] \equiv 2\pi f_p r \equiv w r \equiv \bar{v} \equiv m a = m g = \bar{c}$ then

Stress $\{ \sigma \Phi \} \equiv \left[\frac{2B}{\pi r^3} \right] \equiv 2\pi \cdot f_p r \equiv w r \equiv \bar{v} \equiv m a = m g = \bar{c}$ is dependent on Total-Prior.

5..As soon as $\rightarrow A = \{ \text{The Space + Anti-Space Positions in Universe} \}$, become **Inadequate**

for an **min-Energy-Storage** $A = e^{-i \cdot \left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) \cdot b} = 0,207879576 \cdot b = 1,507 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ m}$, then **Motion**

\equiv **Energy** is first filling **The minimum cave** , r , and with the Necessary **Velocity-Vectors**

\rightarrow **Burst Into another cave** $a > A = 1,507 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ m}$ in L_p , **connected to G** , and which

Is an Overflow of the Energy in the , **Space + Anti-Space Positions** [58] . From relation

$E_{ph} \equiv \bar{c} \cdot \{ \boxed{\bar{f}_n} + f_n \}$ is seen the Storages and from $\bar{q}_{\text{photon}} \equiv \frac{\bar{c} \cdot \sigma\Phi}{2\pi r} \equiv \frac{\bar{w} \cdot \sigma\Phi}{2\pi}$ the Stresses .

Exists $1 \text{ KPa} = 10^3 \text{ Pa}$, $1 \text{ MPa} = 10^6 \text{ Pa}$, $1 \text{ GPa} = 10^9 \text{ Pa}$, $q = \text{itAs} = \text{Cb}$,

$1 \text{ eV} = [1,6022 \cdot 10^{-19} \text{ Cb}]$, $1 \text{ V} = 1,6022 \cdot 10^{-19} \text{ Joule}$, $q_e = 1,6022 \cdot 10^{-19} \text{ Culomb}$,

The Density of Electric current becomes from the Electron- Orbit-motion as equation

$J = \frac{i}{A} = \sigma_{n\text{-max}} = \frac{v_{n\text{-max}}}{\Phi} = \frac{\text{Amper}}{\text{m}^2} = \frac{w_n}{\Phi}$, **Energy** becomes from the maximum velocity as ,

$$E_{n\text{-max}} = \frac{m_e \cdot [v_{n\text{-max}}]^2}{2} = \frac{9,1 \cdot 10^{-31} \text{ Kg} \cdot [v_{n\text{-max}}/s]^2}{2} = \text{Joule} .$$

4.C..Application of Stress σ , on the Walls of Jericho .

DATA :

From Biblical Account and Historical & Archaeological Context ,

a). Wall construction from **Limestones** with Stress $\sigma_L = 2000 - 2500 \text{ Kg/m}^3$.

b). The Wall **Thickness** = 1,50 m , and Height = 7,50 m ,

c). The Wall's **Natural = Frequency** $f_{NF} = 121,72 \text{ Hz}$.

d). Trumpet **Frequency** $f_{TF} = 1400 \text{ Hz}$, and Rams` Horn = 260 -1100 Hz.

e). **Modulating** the Trumpet Frequency $f_{TF} = 1400 \text{ Hz}$, and wind-gusts = 1-Hz = **700,5 Hz**

From equations $f = \frac{\sigma_S \Phi}{2 \cdot \pi r}$, wavelength $\lambda = c / f = 2r$, Resonance frequency $f_R = \frac{\sigma_S \Phi}{\pi \cdot \lambda}$.

From Resonance frequency $f_R = \frac{\sigma_S \Phi}{\pi \cdot \lambda}$. and for wavelength $\lambda_W = \frac{\sigma_S \Phi}{\pi \cdot f_R} = 1,50 \text{ m}$. then \rightarrow

1..For minimum -Stress $\sigma_L = 2000 \rightarrow f_R = \frac{[1,608] \cdot 2000}{\pi \cdot 1,50} = 681,18 \text{ Hz}$, Potentially from (d) - f_{TF}

2..For maximum -Stress $\sigma_L = 2500 \rightarrow f_R = \frac{[1,608] \cdot 2500}{\pi \cdot 1,50} = 853,07 \text{ Hz}$, Potentially from (d) - f_{TF}

3..From Hard-Limestone $\sigma_L = 2500 \rightarrow f_R = \frac{[1,608] \cdot 2300}{\pi \cdot 1,50} = 784,82 \text{ Hz}$, Potentially from (d) - f_{TF}

4..From **Modulated-Frequency** $f_M = 700,5 \text{ Hz}$, then $\sigma_L = \frac{\pi \cdot \lambda \cdot f_M}{\Phi} = 2052,88 \text{ Kg/m}^3$.

Remarks :

a.. At first the Resonance frequency of the collected shouting and Rams` Horn is the Potentially cause of weaken and collapse the Walls.

b.. The Modulated - Frequency of the Trumpet and the wind-gusts is the most possibility to collapse the Walls , and this because of the Limestone very Low stress Resistance .

5.C.. The Parallel Postulate and Relativity : [38]

AB is a straight line through Points A, B and M any other point . When $MA+MB > AB$ then Point M is not on AB .(differently if $MA+MB = AB$ then this answers the question of why any line contains at least two Points i.e. for any Point M on line AB where is holding $MA+MB = AB$, meaning that lines MA , MB coincide on AB / is thus proved from the other axioms and so D2 is not an axiom).

To Prove that , One and only One line MM' can be drawn Parallel to AB.

To Prove the above Axiom is necessary to show:

1...The Parallel to AB is the locus of all Points at a constant distance h from the line AB, and for Point M is MA,

2...The locus of all these Points is a straight line.

Figure – 6 - : The Three Points .

Step 1

Draw the circle (M, MA) be joined meeting line AB in C. Since $MA = MC$, Point M is on mid-Perpendicular of AC. Let A_1 be the midpoint of AC, (it is $A_1A+A_1C = AC$ because A_1 is on the straight line AC. Triangles MAA_1, MCA_1 are equal because the three sides are equal, therefore angle $\angle MA_1A = \angle MA_1C$ (CN₁) and since the sum of the two angles $\angle MA_1A + \angle MA_1C = 180^\circ$ (CN2, 6D) then angle $\angle MA_1A = \angle MA_1C = 90^\circ$.(P4) so, MA_1 is the minimum fixed distance h of Point M to AC. A'

Step 2 .

Let B_1 be the midpoint of CB,(it is $B_1C+B_1B = CB$ because B_1 is on the straight line CB) and draw $B_1M' = h$ equal to A_1M on the mid-perpendicular from Point B_1 to CB. Draw the circle (M', M'B = M'C) intersecting the circle (M, MA = MC) at Point D.(P3) Since $M'C = M'B$, Point M' lies on mid-Perpendicular of CB. (CN₁)

Since $M'C = M'D$, Point M' lies on mid-perpendicular of CD. (CN₁) Since $MC = MD$, Point M lies on mid-perpendicular of CD. (CB₁) Because Points M and M' lie on the same mid-perpendicular (This mid-perpendicular is drawn from point C' to CD and it is the mid Point of CD) and because only one line MM' passes through points M , M' then line MM' coincides with this mid-perpendicular (CN4)

Step 3

Draw the Perpendicular of CD at Point C' . (P3, P1)

- a. Because $MA_1 \perp AC$ and also $MC' \perp CD$ then angle $\angle A_1MC' = \angle A_1CC' \dots$ (Cn 2,Cn3,E.I.15)
- b. Because $M'B_1 \perp CB$ and also $M'C' \perp CD$ then angle $\angle B_1M'C' = \angle B_1CC' \dots$ (Cn2, Cn3, E.I.15)
- c. The sum of angles $\angle A_1CC' + \angle B_1CC' = 180^\circ = \angle A_1MC' + \angle B_1M'C'$. (6.D), and since Point C' lies on straight line MM' , therefore the sum of angles in shape $A_1B_1M'M$ are $\angle MA_1B_1 + \angle A_1B_1M' + [\angle B_1M'M + \angle M'MA_1] = 90^\circ + 90^\circ + 180^\circ = 360^\circ$ (Cn2), i.e.The sum of angles in a Quadrilateral is 360° and in Rectangle all equal to 90° . (m)

- d. The right-angled triangles MA_1B_1 , $M'B_1A_1$ are equal because $A_1M = B_1M'$ and A_1B_1 common, therefore side $A_1M' = B_1M$ (Cn1). Triangles A_1MM' , $B_1M'M$ are equal because have the three sides equal each other, therefore angle $\angle A_1MM' = \angle B_1M'M$, and since their sum is 180° as before (6D), so angle $\angle A_1MM' = \angle B_1M'M = 90^\circ$ (Cn2).
- e. Since angle $\angle A_1MM' = \angle B_1CC'$ and also angle $\angle BIM'M = \angle B_1CC'$ (P4), therefore quadrilaterals $A_1CC'M$, $B_1CC'M'$, $A_1B_1M'M$ are Rectangles (CN3). From the above three rectangles and because all points (M, M' and C') equidistant from AB, this means that C'C is also the minimum equal distance of point C' to line AB or, $h = MA_1 = M'B_1 = CD/2 = C'C$ (Cn1) Namely, line MM' is Perpendicular to segment CD at Point C' and this line coincides with the mid-perpendicular of CD at this Point C' and points M, M', C' are on line MM'. Point C' equidistant ,h, from line AB, as it is for points M, M', so the locus of the three Points is the straight line MM', so the two demands are satisfied, ($h = C'C = MA_1 = M'B_1$ and also $C'C \perp AB$, $MA_1 \perp AB$, $M'B_1 \perp AB$). (o.e.d.)
- The right-angle triangles A_1CM , MCC' are equal because side $MA_1 = C'C$ and MC common so angle $\angle A_1CM = \angle C'MC$, and the Sum of angles $\angle C'MC + \angle MCB_1 = \angle B_1CM + \angle MCB_1 = 180^\circ$

Conclusions :

- 1.. From any Point M, there is only one Parallel to any A-B, Straight line .
- 2.. From Point M, there is only one Parallel to, $A - B \rightarrow \infty$, Straight line .
- 3.. From Point M, there is only one Parallel to, $B - A \rightarrow \infty$, Straight line .
- 4..The light-rays and consequently the Photons travel in Straight lines, i.e. follow the Euclidean Geometry and NOT any other .
- 5..Time is the meter, to measure the changes in Energy = **motion** = Force x displacement, and NOT any other essence .The essence of Universe is \rightarrow Space $\equiv [\oplus \leftarrow r \rightarrow \ominus]$, Energy $\equiv [\oplus \sigma \ominus] \leftarrow$
- 6..The Gravitational force G, causes the Bending of the light rays (of Photons), and Not the warping of Spacetime, which meaning is Not existing because this Concept has never been clarified .

6.C.. The Duality Of Isochronous – Photons : [77]

Photon is the first Propagating **Material-Point** in existing Universe in where ,

- 1.. The Space and the Anti-Space are linearly effecting and equilibrium . .
- 2.. The Space and the Anti-Space are Perpendicularly effecting and equilibrium .
- 3.. The Space and the Anti-Space are Torsionally effecting and equilibrium .

Figure – 7- : The Material-Geometry Mechanism of motion in Photons-Cave :

FROM MECHANICS **The Eternal-Rotation** of the Two Elements , $[\oplus \cup \ominus]$, Up or Down in Material Point circles ,Originates the Spins , $\pm \frac{1}{2}$, ± 1 , $\mp \frac{1}{2}$, of All Particles Fermions or and Bosons which combine from above Three-States just by Adding their Spins [36] . From Cauchy-Stress-Tensor under Plane-Stress conditions the **Equation of Principal-Stresses** $\sigma_{1,2}$, is $\sigma_{1/2} = \pm$

$\pm (\frac{1}{2}) \cdot \sqrt{\sigma_1^2 + 4 \cdot \sigma_2^2} = \sigma_1 \cdot [1 \pm (\sqrt{5})] / 2 = \sigma \cdot \Phi$, which is the **Golden-ratio-Pattern** of the Material Point as Type of a vanishing Shear due to layers laterally shifted . Equilibrium of , ABCD , ABFE , CDEF Quadrilaterals is through Ptolemy`s and Ceba`s Equilibrium - relations , Fig-14 .

The above Material Point is the Energy-Structure of Photon which is Quantized and Equilibrium.

Stability of Photon`s construction of , ABCD , Rectangle issues through **Ptolemy`s -Theorem** for **Inner - Connectors** $[AC \cdot BD = AB \cdot CD + AD \cdot CB]$, and the **Ceba`s Theorem** for the three **Outer Connectors** of , ABCD , CDEF , Rectangles as $\rightarrow [CD \cdot AE \cdot FB = CB \cdot FE \cdot AD]$, BDEF , Rectangle as $\rightarrow [BD \cdot AE \cdot GF = BF \cdot GE \cdot AD]$, AEFC , Rectangle as $\rightarrow [AE \cdot GF \cdot BC = AC \cdot BF \cdot GE]$. With this Way is succeeded the Stability of the whole structure of Photon .

This minimum quantized Energy σ , was Proved that is going out the Material Point , *because of Skin effect* , as acceleration and creates the Stationary gravity g as f_n , acting on Spin as $S_{PA} \cdot r^4$. The Centripetal Force and equal to Stress σ , is $F_c = mv^2 / r =$

$$\frac{d^2s}{dt^2} = -g \cdot \frac{s}{4r} \text{ or } \{ \ddot{s} = -w^2 \dot{s} \cdot (wr)^2 / r = w^2 \cdot r = \pm \sigma = (2\pi \cdot f_1)^2 \cdot r =$$

$\sigma_1 \cdot [1 \pm (\sqrt{5})] / 2 = \Phi \cdot \sigma$, and since mass is $m = \frac{\sigma}{w^2 \cdot r} = \frac{\sigma}{w \cdot c} = \frac{\bar{B}}{r \cdot c}$ then , $\pm \sigma = \frac{c \cdot \bar{B}}{r^2}$ which is a relation between Stress Momentum and light-velocity c . It was shown in [70-P32] that in a Cycloid , the area between the curve and the straight line is $A = 3\pi r^2$ and the arc length $l = 8r$. For the motion on cycloid , we consider a Weight Q , at a point A , moving with free motion.

Since reaction N is vertically acting , doesn`t give any Tangential component therefore the only one becomes from Q ,which is equal to $AT = g \cdot \sin \varphi$ and since $\sin \varphi = \frac{s}{4r}$ and then $AT = g \cdot \frac{s}{4r}$. Since acceleration $a = \frac{d^2s}{dt^2} = \frac{dv}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt}(\frac{ds}{dt}) = -g \cdot \frac{s}{4r}$ then *where* $w = \frac{2\pi}{T} = \frac{g}{4r}$ } ... (a) which (a) is a Harmonic Oscillatory motion showing that Acceleration is proportional to displacement

and is directed towards the origin with a Period $T = \frac{2\pi}{w} = 2\pi \cdot \sqrt{\frac{4r}{g}} = 4\pi \cdot \sqrt{\frac{r}{g}}$, or and $w^2 = [\frac{g}{4r}]^2$, where

$w = 2\pi f$. **Origination of Frequency , or Period** , happens from above Property where

$w = [\frac{g}{4r}] = 2\pi f$. In Material-Point the Cycloidal-acceleration g_{cyc} is transformed as Centrifugal

acceleration $g_{cyc} = \frac{(v)^2}{R} = \frac{g}{4r}$, where r = the Radius of the Cycloidal-circle and R = the radius of curvature . In Cycloid velocity-vector $\bar{v} \equiv \bar{\sigma}$, and it is the Glue-Bond-Stress between the Opposites

\oplus , \ominus so velocity $\bar{v} = \bar{w} \cdot r = 2\pi \cdot \bar{f} \cdot r = \bar{\sigma} = \sigma \Phi$, the Frequency $\bar{f} = \frac{\bar{\sigma} = [\sigma \Phi]}{2\pi r}$ and the Total-Energy

$2L = J \cdot w^2 = 4\pi^2 \cdot f^2$. The Circular frequency is $w^2 = \frac{(\sigma \Phi)^2}{r^2} = [2\pi f]^2$, and the **Frequency of Photon**

$$\text{is } \rightarrow f_p = \left| \frac{\sigma \Phi}{2\pi r} \right| = \frac{[1 + \sqrt{5}] \sigma}{4\pi r} = \frac{\sigma \cdot \Phi}{2\pi r} \dots\dots (a) \text{ i.e.}$$

Equation (a) denotes that the Harmonic - Oscillation due to Any-Force or Weight , which Follows the free motion on Cycloid , is Independent of the Amplitude of oscillation and , is Isochronous . This Property belongs to Photon also , since it is a Material - Point . [70]

Since Total-Energy $L = B w = \frac{J \cdot w}{2} w = \frac{J \cdot w^2}{2}$ then $2L = J \cdot w^2$, and $\bar{B} = r \cdot mv = r \cdot \frac{\pi r^4}{2} 2\pi f r = \pi^2 \cdot r^4 \cdot f$.

From momentum relation $\bar{B} = m r v = m r^2 w = m r^2 (2\pi f) = \frac{J \cdot w}{2} = [\frac{\pi r^4}{2}] \cdot [2\pi f]$ then **Spin S** \equiv

$$\equiv \text{Angular-momentum } \bar{B} \equiv \bar{S} = \frac{J \cdot w}{2} = \frac{\pi r^4}{2} [2\pi f] = \pi^2 \cdot r^4 \cdot [f] \equiv \frac{[1 + \sqrt{5}] \cdot \sigma \cdot \pi \cdot r^3}{4} = \frac{\pi r^3 \Phi \cdot \sigma}{2} \dots\dots (b)$$

Frequency of Photon is $f_n = \frac{[(1 + \sqrt{5}) \sigma]}{4\pi r} = \frac{\sigma \Phi}{2\pi r}$, where $\Phi = \frac{(1 + \sqrt{5})}{2} = 1,6180339887$ and , $2r$

is The Diameter of Energy-Cave $AB = 2r$ of circle $(O,OA) = \text{Monad} \rightarrow \oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus \equiv 1 + \Phi$ and

$BC = |\sigma| =$ The **Glue-Bond-Vector** , $\oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus$, from the main-Stresses magnitude .

$ABCD = |\sigma| \cdot |\Phi + 1| =$ The **Energy-Space** Rectangular Parallelogram in Plane ABC .

$ABFE = -|\sigma| \cdot |\Phi + 1| =$ The **Energy-Anti-Space** Rectangular Parallelogram in Plane ABC

$BF = |\Phi \cdot \sigma| =$ **The Anti-Space-Vector** , and $FG = |\Phi| =$ The **Space-Vector** magnitude .

In circle of AB diameter is created the Stress $\sigma = BC$ and both the Resultant-monad $BD = AC$.
From Kepler 2nd Orbit laws the Unit-Quantized-Area , or Unit Quantized Energy is that per /sec
 $\rightarrow r \, d\phi$, following equation $1 = k \cdot f_u^2 \cdot r^3$, and expresses the area of triangles in Fig-8 .

In Figure \rightarrow Triangle 2(ABC) = BC.BA = $\sigma \cdot [\Phi + 1] \equiv \sigma \cdot \Phi + \sigma =$ [**Stress-In-Storage- Φ**] +

[**Moving-Stress**] Or **Storage S** \equiv [$\oplus \leftarrow r \equiv \Phi \rightarrow \ominus$] + **Motion M** \equiv [$\bar{v} - \text{Vector}$]

and from Figure -3- where Stress σ is the motion and $\sigma \Phi$ the Storage , issues Geometry ,

Triangle 2(BFG) = FB.FG = $\sigma \cdot \Phi[\Phi] = \sigma \cdot \Phi^2 = \sigma \cdot [\Phi + 1] \equiv \sigma \cdot \Phi + \sigma \equiv S_{\text{storage}} + M_{\text{motion}}$

Triangle 2(DEG) = EG.ED = $\sigma + \sigma \Phi = \sigma \cdot [1 + \Phi] \equiv \sigma \cdot \Phi + \sigma \equiv S_{\text{storage}} + M_{\text{motion}}$, and

since Energy = motion / T $\equiv (\frac{v}{2\pi r}) \cdot [\sigma + \sigma \Phi] = \bar{v} \cdot [\frac{\sigma}{2\pi r} + \frac{\sigma \Phi}{2\pi r}] \equiv \bar{v} \cdot [\bar{f}_n + f_n] \equiv$

Moving - Storage $\rightarrow [\bar{v} \cdot \bar{f}_n] \leftarrow$ + Moving-Frequency $\rightarrow [\bar{v} \cdot f_n] \leftarrow \equiv$ Material-Point i.e.

The Energy produced in Photon-Cave is consisted of **Two-moving-Storages** , that travel

as Wave $[\bar{v} \cdot f_n] \rightarrow [\bar{v} \cdot \bar{f}_n] \rightarrow [\bar{v} = \bar{c} = \lambda \frac{f}{\Phi}] \rightarrow [S \equiv EM-R \equiv f_{1=N}, f_2, f_3, f_D, f_n = w^2]$ and ,

as Particle $\rightarrow [f_1 = (E^2 + H^2) = n \frac{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma}{2\pi r} = \frac{nB}{\pi^2 r^4}] \rightarrow \{W \equiv EM-R \equiv [\epsilon E^2 + \mu B^2] = 2 \cdot \lambda \cdot c \cdot \sin 2\phi\}$ and ,

The Duality of an Energy-Storage $S \equiv \{ [\oplus \leftarrow r \rightarrow \ominus] + \text{Motion M} \equiv [\bar{v} - \text{Vector}] \}$,

Therefore \rightarrow Photon is travelling Both as Particle and as Wave , as

1.. **Energy-Storage S** $\equiv [\oplus \leftarrow r \rightarrow \ominus] \equiv$ Particle $[\bar{v} \cdot \bar{f}_n] \rightarrow [\bar{v} = \bar{c} = \lambda \frac{f}{\Phi}] \rightarrow$ i.e.

a **Stationary Standing - Wave** $\rightarrow [S \equiv [EM-R \equiv f_{1=N}, f_2, f_3, f_D, f_n = w^2]]$.

2.. **Energy-Motion M** $\equiv [\bar{v} - \text{Vector}] \equiv$ The **Wave** $[\bar{v} \cdot f_n] \equiv [f_1 = (E^2 + H^2) = n \frac{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma}{2\pi r} =$

$\frac{B}{\pi^2 r^4}] \rightarrow$ i.e. a **Propagating Wave** as $\rightarrow \{W \equiv EM-R \equiv [\epsilon E^2 + \mu B^2] = 2 \cdot \lambda \cdot c \cdot \sin 2\phi [\phi = \frac{B}{\Phi}]\} \leftarrow$

7.C.. The moving Storages of Photons and The Stability of Dual-frequency f_{photon} :

Photon is a Material-Point in cave r , where its **Inner** is *the Stationary-Standing-wave from*

Electromagnetic-Wave $[E^2 + H^2] = 2(2r) \cdot c \cdot \sin 2\phi$ with n Lobes representing the

Normal mode vibration with frequencies $f_n = n \cdot f_1 = \frac{E}{h} = \frac{n \cdot v}{4r} = \frac{n\sigma}{8r} [1 + \sqrt{5}]$, and its

Outward is as the *Propagating Electromagnetic-Wave* $\rightarrow \{[\epsilon E^2 + \mu B^2] = 2 \cdot \lambda \cdot c \cdot \sin 2\phi\} \leftarrow$

where Particle $2r = n \lambda$, **Cave** r , is the *Electromagnetic-Energy-Storage* , and Electromagnetic-
Radiation E, B is the *Wave conveyer* . Following above constituents of Photon then , Since **Energy**

is motion and the *Total - Energy of Elementary - Particle* is equal to the \rightarrow **Intrinsic Rotational + Kinetic Energy from velocity** , then according to the conservation law of Energy , **This Energy is stored into Neutral caves as Stationary Loops consisting the Lobes** , and thus producing the **Space and the Anti - Space Particles with velocity vector the remaining of the Energy Term** .

It is proved that Hydrogen cave is the lightest and less-mass element .

The Breakage - Principle , is the way of **Energy conservation** , where **Energy never annihilates and which is always reverted into** \rightarrow the two Opposites $\{(\pm w)$ or the Conveyers \equiv Carriers $\}$ and an **Neutral Part** $2 \cdot \nabla i$ which is the Energy-store \equiv a Tank \equiv The Magnetic fields .

Energy \equiv or as **Matter** $(+ w)$, as **Antimatter** $(- w)$ and as **Energy Part** , $2L = \bar{B} \cdot \bar{w}$

i.e. **Energy \equiv Motion \equiv Space + Anti space + Kinetic Energy** ,

Vibrations of Systems issues for Orbits as $\rightarrow W = 4\pi^2 \cdot \frac{r^3}{T^2} \cdot \bar{n} = 4\pi^2 \cdot r^3 \cdot f_p^2 \cdot \bar{n} \leftarrow$ and agree , to

Kepler celestial law such as for *macrocosm and for microcosm* .

Using the Material-Geometry-Vectors for the **Anti-Space Action** then ,

From Force $G_{ON-AntiSpace} = \overline{AB} \times \overline{BF} \equiv [\Phi+1] \times \{ |\overline{\sigma}| \cdot \Phi \equiv \sigma \cdot \Phi \} = \Phi^2 \cdot \sigma \Phi = \sigma \cdot \Phi^3$, or ,

$G_{AN} \equiv \overline{AB} \times \overline{BC} \equiv \sigma \cdot \Phi^3 \equiv \boxed{\overline{\sigma} - \text{Stress}} \boxed{[\oplus \leftarrow \Phi \rightarrow \ominus]} \boxed{[\oplus \leftarrow \Phi \rightarrow \ominus]} \boxed{[\oplus \leftarrow \Phi \rightarrow \ominus]}$

and $\rightarrow \rightarrow \rightarrow$ **Primary-Energy** $\equiv G \cdot f_p \equiv h$ and OR $G^{-1} \times \sigma \times \Phi^3 \equiv 1 \leftarrow \leftarrow \leftarrow$ where

$G \equiv$ The Newton`s-Universal Force = $6,680561 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3/\text{Ns}^2$

$\sigma \equiv$ The Glue-Bond-Stress in Material-Points $\sigma = \frac{2\pi r f}{\Phi} = 1,85 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ Kg/m}^2$ and , f ,

in Planck`s length $r = L_p = e^{-i \cdot (5\pi/2) \cdot 10}$ is the Frequency $f_{\text{Planck}} = \frac{c}{2\pi r} = 2,952362 \cdot 10^{42} \text{ H}$,

in Planck`s Length $L_p = e^{-i \cdot (5\pi/2) \cdot 10} = \{ \sqrt{3} \cdot \pi \cdot 1,616199 \cdot 10^{-35} \text{ m} \}$

$\Phi \equiv$ The Golden-Ratio Pattern $\Phi = \frac{(1+\sqrt{5})}{2} = 1,6180339887$

From above relations is seen that , in Universe exists the only one Force $G \equiv \sigma \cdot \Phi^3$, which is

Acting on all **Quantized-Quantities** as $\rightarrow G \equiv \sigma \cdot \Phi^3 \equiv \Phi^2 \cdot \{ \sigma \Phi \} \equiv 2\pi f_p r \equiv w r \equiv \vec{v} \equiv m a = \vec{c} \leftarrow$

and From $\sigma \times \Phi^3 \equiv G \rightarrow [1,846462 \cdot 10^{-11}] \cdot [3,618033989] = 6,680561 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ o.e.}\delta.(\mathbf{q.e.d})$

i.e. Universe is a Monad , Becoming from a **HUGE-MAGNET** of Opposites \oplus , \ominus which Forms $>$

\rightarrow The 3-Dimensional **SPACES** Φ , **ANTI-SPACES** $|\Phi \cdot \sigma|$, and $> \rightarrow$ Energy , where

ENERGY \equiv **MOTION** through the **G** - Force , and the Stress - σ - becoming from Photon .

Or . **The Ubiquity of Material-Geometry in Electromagnetism** is Everywhere .

Remarks on the **Duality-Photon** $\rightarrow \{ \vec{c} \cdot \boxed{\vec{f}_n} + \vec{c} \cdot f_n \} \leftarrow \equiv \rightarrow$ Particle + Wave \leftarrow

- a.. From equations $f = \frac{\sigma_1 \Phi}{2\pi r}$ and $\sigma_1 \cdot [1 \pm (\sqrt{5})] / 2 = \sigma \cdot \Phi$, then **Frequency** f_p , of Photon , is Independent of the Amplitude $[\epsilon E^2 + \mu B^2]$ of the Vibration , it is **Not-Damped and Not-Driven** , and so can be related to **Any-Force that can Produce Work** \equiv **Energy as Wave** and thus can be **Quantized to any Monad** . The Electromagnetic-Spectrum \equiv **Photon** in all its frequencies , which as **Frequency** f , or as **Period** T , is the Regulator of the Light - Signals .
- b.. **Photon** striking on an Object of Microcosm or Macrocosm then , **It is a Source** that **Gives** \rightarrow **Energy** as Energy-Storage , $\boxed{\vec{f}_n}$, and **Information** as the G-Ratio Propagating - Energy f_n .
- c.. **Photon** in the Microcosm of Hydrogen-Cave can-Give such **Potential-Energy or Resonance Energy** as **Frequency** f_R and Energy in [**Bracket-Orbit-Hook**] which Joins the **Atoms to Produce** the **Molecules and Crystals** , MRI Photos and all Spectrum frequencies .
- d.. **Photon** striking on **Hydrogen-Cave** can Produce the **Resonance-Energy-Frequency** f_R , such that can Produce **Photos** and **Image-Fringes** of Inter-Atom or any other Structures in Atoms .
- e.. **Photon** striking on **Cells** can Produce a **Resonance-Energy-Frequency** f_R , such that can **Enter Cell** and **Break-It-Up** . Duality-Photon Places the Storages $\boxed{\vec{f}_n}$ everywhere then it stops and diffuses. The **Kinetic-Energy** E_K of a moving Material - Point , as this is the Photon , is stored as motion in its Storage , $r = [n \lambda/2]$ with the , n frequencies $f_n = n \cdot f_1$, with n lobes and with the fundamental frequency f_1 .

From above is seen the **Passage and The -How EM-Radiation can travel in Crystals** and which are the **Cauchy-Stress-Tensor** where $E \perp B \perp r \equiv \sigma_1 \perp \sigma_2 \perp \sigma_3$, in-where Energy Propagates along 3 Directions **without Birefringence** which are the tracks of the Stresses , and carries the motion \equiv Energy Storage r which radiation is **The Conveyer** , the Storages $\boxed{\vec{f}_n}$, **the Magnetic fields** .

Above procedure can be used in **Cells** where cells are cases of a **Birefringence material** and their

Resonance Passage happens as the Force of *EM-Radiation in Two directions*, can travel in Cell through *Cauchy Stress Tensor* where the Two Conveyers $E \perp B \perp r \equiv \sigma_1 \perp \sigma_2 \perp \sigma_3$, can carry the Energy-Storage, r , in Cell. Interfacial Properties are detected from Surfactant, and can change the *Inner-Structure of Cell to another desirable Property*. A wide Analysis in [84-86-90].

Moreover, in open Conductors the Conductor's Resultant-energy-Vector is as an **Cruise-missile** where for Primary-Forces Energies $|k_x.k_y| = |\leftrightarrow|.|\downarrow| \equiv \otimes$ become very strong **Cruise-Ballistic-missile**.

8.C..The Quantum Interference of the Duality-Photon :

Quantum Interference is the Phenomenon when, a Photon Interferes with itself. [92E]
 This Proposition is Right when Photon is considered having a twin-existence, which is [101]3c.P-21
 The Problem is to determine the expression of the Power developed by Gravitational
 From Dual-Photon-equation, $\vec{v} \cdot [\vec{f}_n + f_n] \equiv |\frac{v}{\pi^2.r^4_n}| \cdot |\vec{B}_n| + |\vec{c}| f_n$, when $\vec{c} = 0$ or $\vec{c} = \vec{c}$, then **Photon motion** becomes $\rightarrow |\frac{v}{\pi^2.r^4_n}| \cdot |\vec{B}_n| \leftarrow \equiv \text{Spin}$. i.e. **The Stationary Photons exist as their Spin only.**
 This **Rest-Space** is the Part $|\frac{v}{\pi^2.r^4_n}| \cdot |\vec{B}_n|$, and its Communication Code to be the term $|\frac{v}{\pi^2.r^4_n}| = |\frac{wr}{\pi^2.r^4}| = |\frac{2v}{2\pi^3r^4}|$, The Rest Space is a Stationary Wave with fundamental frequency $f_1 = \frac{1}{T_1} = \frac{\lambda}{c}$, with an Electric Wave, that is acting on vector $\vec{c} = (i.c_x + j.c_y)$. It was proved [78] that the Newton's Gravitational constant G does NOT effect on Plane Surfaces, but on Volume Surfaces only..

This Property of G, means that the only one Force which effects on the Rest-Space in Torsional motion, and on the light velocity vector \vec{c} , is the gravity g only.

Figure - 8- : The Stability of $\rightarrow \{ \oplus - \text{Space [Electric Wave] } , \{ \ominus - \text{Anti-Space [Magnetic Wave] } \}$ of the Sub-Space $\{ [\oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus] \equiv ds \equiv [\oplus \leftrightarrow -ds \rightarrow \ominus] - \text{or} - \text{The Neutral-Space [} A_E, B_E, C_E \} :$

Since c is constant, it is analyzed to, (c_x, c_y) in any two directions x, y where $x \perp y$ and y to be the gravity direction on where gravity is acting.

The Produced Work is in y -Range, $S_y = c_y t - \frac{1}{2} g t^2 = c \sin at - \frac{1}{2} g t^2$, where maximum Range is

$$S_{\max-y} = c_y^2 / 2g = \frac{(c \sin at)^2}{2g} = \left[\frac{c^2}{2g}\right] \sin^2 a, \text{ happening at angle } a = 90^\circ \text{ and where } \sin^2 a = 1.$$

Since at Point (1) the velocity $v_y = 0$, the motion in 0-1, maybe considered as falling in linear motion and so issues $v_y = g t$ or time $t = \frac{v_y}{g} = \frac{(c \sin at)}{g}$, as halve Period with total Period $\rightarrow T = \frac{2(c \sin at)}{g}$.

In figure are seen the 4-Point Positions, at where change the Phase and the Work done in each Phase of Photon's inner motion. The 4-Phases correspond to the Wavelength λ , as $\lambda / 4$ distance with $90^\circ = \frac{\pi}{2}$ to be the change of Phase. **This means that the Produced Work in Prior Phase-Area as Golden - Ratio Pattern is Stored in the Next and Perpendicular Phase-Area.**

The Total distance for doing Work is the Wavelength λ , in total Period T as $\lambda = c_x T = c \cdot \cos a \cdot T$

$$\text{or } \lambda = c \cdot \cos a \cdot \frac{2(c \sin at)}{g} = \left[\frac{2c^2}{g}\right] \sin a \cdot \cos a = \left[\frac{c^2}{g}\right] \sin 2a, \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

since from trigonometry exists, $\sin 2a = 2 \sin a \cdot \cos a$.

The maximum wavelength λ happens when $\sin 2a = 1$ or $2a = 90^\circ$ and $a = 45^\circ$, i.e., $\rightarrow \rightarrow$

The Total motion in the Wavelength, λ , corresponds to the angle $a = 45^\circ$, meaning that the motion of Space, *The Electric-field*-, and Anti-space, *The Magnetic-field*, equilibrium as an Bellow. The two Wings in 90° Type simultaneously oscillate to its 45° Bisector-axis, and the Produced Work from *The Electric-field-area*, is Stored into *the Magnetic - field - area*. The common axis of the two Perpendicular fields, carry the *G-Ratio Surfaces*, Runs with the same velocity \bar{c} to the direction of the inner motion \rightarrow

or,

From $90^\circ \rightarrow 45^\circ$, the created Work $W = c_y g$, and is Symmetrically Stored from $0^\circ \rightarrow 45^\circ$

The created Work in [0-1] is in $\rightarrow \lambda / 4$ of transverse surface and is stored in the horizontal and perpendicular surface [1`-2] = $\lambda / 4$. Surface [0-1-1`] = \perp Surface [1`-2`-2].

The created Work in [1-2] is in $\rightarrow \lambda / 4$ of transverse surface and is stored in the horizontal and perpendicular surface [2-3`] = $\lambda / 4$. Surface [1-2-1`] = \perp Surface [2`-3`-2].

The created Work in [2-3] is in $\rightarrow \lambda / 4$ of transverse surface and is stored in the horizontal and perpendicular surface [3`-4] = $\lambda / 4$. Surface [2-3-3`] = \perp Surface [3`-4`-4`].

The created Work in [3-4] is in $\rightarrow \lambda / 4$ of transverse surface and is stored in the horizontal and perpendicular surface [3`-4] = $\lambda / 4$. Surface [3-4-2] = \perp Surface [4`-5`-4].

Since from Trigonometry issues $\sin 2\pi = \sin(180 - 2a) = \sin 2(90 - a)$ then (1) becomes .

$$\lambda = c \cos a \frac{2(c \sin at)}{g} = \left[\frac{2c^2}{g}\right] \sin a \cdot \cos a = \left[\frac{c^2}{g}\right] \sin 2a = \left[\frac{c^2}{g}\right] \cdot \sin(\pi - 2a) = \left[\frac{c^2}{g}\right] \cdot \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{2} - a\right) \dots(2)$$

since $\sin 2a = \sin(180 - 2a) = \sin(\pi - 2a)$, and also $\sin 2a = \sin(180 - 2a) = \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{2} - a\right)$

From Dual-Photon-equation, $\bar{v} \cdot \left[\overline{f_n} + f_n \right] \equiv \left| \frac{v}{\pi^2 \cdot r^4_n} \right| \cdot \overline{B_n} + |\bar{c}| f_n$, when $c = 0$ or $\bar{c} = \bar{c}$, then **Photon motion** becomes $\rightarrow \left| \frac{v}{\pi^2 \cdot r^4_n} \right| \cdot \overline{B_n} \leftarrow \equiv \text{Spin}$. i.e. **The Stationary Photons exist as their Spin only.**

The **Rest-Space** is the Part $\left| \frac{v}{\pi^2 \cdot r^4_n} \right| \cdot \overline{B_n}$ where $v = n \cdot \pi \cdot c$, and Communication Code to be the term $\left| \frac{v}{\pi^2 \cdot r^4_n} \right| = \left| \frac{n \cdot \pi \cdot c}{\pi^2 \cdot r^4_n} \right| = \left| \frac{n \cdot c}{\pi \cdot r^4} \right| = \left| \frac{w r}{\pi^2 \cdot r^4} \right| = \left| \frac{2 \pi \cdot f}{\pi^2 \cdot r^3} \right| = \left| \frac{2 \cdot f}{(\pi r^3)} \right|$ with **Electromagnetic-Radiation** the in monads **frequency-f**, which is satisfied by the relation $\left| \frac{2(rw)}{2v} \right| = \pi / 2, \pi, 3\pi / 2, \dots, n \cdot [\pi / 2]$, and $w = n \cdot \left[\frac{\bar{v}}{2r} \right] \times \left[\frac{\pi}{2} \right]$,

where $n = 1 \rightarrow \infty$. **When two Photons** strike each other, $\bar{c} = \bar{c}$, or reflect on a wall, then

$c = 0$, and from **Spin** $\bar{S} = \bar{B} = \pi^2 \cdot r^4 \cdot f_1$ its angular velocity $w = n \cdot \left[\frac{\bar{v}}{2r} \right] \times \left[\frac{\pi}{2} \right] = 2\pi \cdot f_1$, where then

its fundamental frequency $f_1 = n \cdot \left[\frac{\bar{v}}{2r}\right] \times \left[\frac{1}{4}\right] = n \cdot \left[\frac{\bar{v}}{8r}\right]$ which for $n = \left[\frac{16 \cdot r^2}{v \cdot c}\right]$ increases to $\frac{\lambda}{c} \cdot r^3$, and Photon-motion becomes $\rightarrow \left|\frac{v}{\pi^2 \cdot r^4 \cdot n}\right| \cdot \left[\bar{B}_n\right] \leftarrow \equiv \text{Spin}$, i.e. **The Stationary Photons are Spin only and consist an Stationary- Harmonic-Vibration with the same Period T of the two Waves** [92-E].

The effective-Range of the Wavelength λ , for the Dual-Photon is related to the consistence v_x, v_y , velocities to any two Perpendicular directions of Electromagnetic fields E_x, E_y . The maximum displacement in y, direction is the centrifugal $\lambda_x = \frac{v^2 y}{2 E_y}$ and since $v_y = c \cdot \sin(\varphi)$ $\lambda_y = \frac{c^2 \cdot \sin^2(\varphi)}{2 E_y}$ where φ = the Phase difference between the two vibrations. Since time t, is the same between the two vibrations where then $t = \frac{v_y}{E_y} = \frac{c \cdot \sin(\varphi)}{E_x}$ and since the Period = 2.t then $T = \frac{2c \cdot \sin(\varphi)}{E_x}$ (2)

From the in x \rightarrow direction velocity $v_x = c \cdot \cos(\varphi)$, and displacements, λ_x, λ_y , become, $\lambda_x = v_x T = c \cdot \cos(\varphi) \left\{ \frac{2c \cdot \sin(\varphi)}{E_x} \right\} = \lambda_x = \left\{ \frac{2 \cdot c^2}{E_x} \right\} \cdot \sin(\varphi) \cdot \cos(\varphi) = \left\{ \frac{c^2}{E_x} \right\} \cdot \sin(2 \cdot \varphi)$ (3)

Since in trigonometry issues, $\sin(2\varphi) = \sin(\pi - 2\varphi) = \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \varphi\right)$ and in Physics $E_x = g$, then

$$\rightarrow \lambda_x = \left\{ \frac{c^2}{g} \right\} \cdot \sin(\pi - 2\varphi), \lambda_y = \left\{ \frac{c^2}{g} \right\} \cdot \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \varphi\right) \leftarrow \dots\dots(4)$$

- i.e. **Photons occupy**
- 1.. **The Dual-Property of Particles and Waves**,
 - 2.. **The Dual-Property of Stationary and Spin**,
 - 3.. **The Dual-Property of Simultaneous existence**,
 - 4.. **As Electric and Magnetic Fields in λ_x, λ_y** ,
 - 5.. **The Bellow motion in transverse E-M- Waves the way to fly**,
 - 6.. **The Transverse E-M- Waves are \perp to Propagation-Direction**,
 - 7.. **The Electric Effective Range is thrust through G only.** [Fig-9] .
 - 8.. **With the same initial velocity is succeeded the same Length-Range with Two complementary angles.**

Remarks :

- 1.. The Produced-Work happens at $\lambda / 4$. wavelength in 4-Phases and it is Quantised .
- 2.. The Quantised-Work in $\lambda / 4$. wavelength is the $\frac{1}{2}$ of the first lobe of the Sinusoidal Wave .
- 3.. Photons follow the Aeroplanes Bellow motion to fly as (thrust - drag , weight - lift) .
- 4.. It was shown that when **Two Photons** strike each other, $\vec{c} = \vec{c}$, or reflect on a wall, **then** $c = 0$ and the produced energy enters the cave r . **The fundamental frequency of the Stationary-cave is** $f_1 = n \frac{\sigma\Phi}{2\pi r} = n \cdot \left[\frac{\bar{v}}{2r}\right] \times \left[\frac{1}{4\pi}\right] = n \cdot \left[\frac{\bar{v}}{8\pi r}\right]$ which for $n = \left[\frac{8\pi r c}{v \cdot \lambda}\right]$ increases to $\frac{\lambda}{c}$, therefore for $n = N \cdot \left[\frac{8\pi r c}{v \cdot \lambda}\right] = N \cdot \left|\frac{8\pi r}{\lambda}\right|$, and for $N \rightarrow \infty$ then $f_1 = E / h = \infty$ (b)

In Dual Photon $\bar{v} \left[\frac{\sigma\Phi}{2\pi r} + \frac{\sigma}{2\pi r} \right] \equiv \bar{v} \cdot \left[\left[\bar{f}_n\right] + f_n \right]$, **Colours are Still-Sub-Units of Storage** $\left[\bar{v} \cdot \left[\bar{f}_n\right] \right]$, and exist as **Frequencies**, Violet, Blue, Green, which Stabilize with their Complementary colors Yellow, Orange, Red, of wavelength $d = \lambda \rightarrow \lambda_{\min} \approx \lambda_{\max} = 3 \cdot 10^{-7} m \approx 3 \cdot \sqrt{3} \cdot 10^{-7} m$

- 4.1.. **The Quanta of Energy**, Passing through a Unit-Surface or Volume is **Inversely Proportional** to the **fourth Power** of the wavelength λ as $I = 0,5865 \cdot \left\{ \frac{1}{\lambda^4} \right\}$. **When** $f_{BE} = E / h = \infty$ then the Energy-Intension Increases and the **wavelength λ Decreases** and for $f_{BE} = \infty$ then $\lambda = 0$.

This is what happens to Photons in **Black-Holes** where $d = \lambda = 0$, and in where $E = f_{BE} = \infty$.

- 4.2.. **The Proton Total- Harmonic- Charge** $\rightarrow Q_T \equiv 2 \cdot q_u + q_d$, and from $d = \lambda$ then $f_p = \sqrt{\frac{k}{m \lambda}}$
Applying the above to **White light**, which is composed of all colours of **visible light** with different

wavelengths ,when it passes through our atmosphere the tiny molecules cause it to scatter . Scattering or the redirectioning , increases as the wavelength of the light decreases .Violet , Blue , Green , have **Shortest** wavelength and **more Scattering** , while Yellow , Red , Dark-Red have **Longest** wavelength and **Shortest Scattering** , as is the Raylight-scattering . Atoms have a common way for Recognizing the **In-Between Electromagnetic Pattern** , and which is through the , **Resonance of tone** ≡

The **Resonance frequency** , $f_R = \sqrt{\frac{k}{M}}$, where k = Their Stiffness and M = The **Harmonic-mass of their Compound** .

In Mechanics , the Kinetic Energy is equal to Potential $E_K = E_P$, and Total Energy $E_T = 2.E_K = 2.E_P$ or $\rightarrow \frac{1}{2} m v_i^2 = \frac{1}{2} k d = \frac{1}{2} m (w r_i)^2$, and for stability issues , $k d = m w^2 . d^2$, or $w^2 = \frac{k}{m} [\frac{1}{d}]$, or $\bar{w} = \sqrt{\frac{k}{m} [\frac{1}{d}]} = 2\pi . f$, and $f = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{k}{md}}$. From Energy equation $E = h f = \frac{h}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{k}{m}} = \frac{6,6260696.10^{-34}}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{k}{m.d}}$

$= 1,054572.10^{-34} \sqrt{\frac{k}{md}} . J = 1,0545717.10^{-34} \sqrt{\frac{k}{m}} / (1,6022.10^{-19} eV) = 6,582022.10^{-16} \sqrt{\frac{k}{m}} . eV = E_K + E_P$, i.e. In Mechanics , The equality of the Two **Opposite-quantities** $E_K = E_P$, is conserved

in a **common loop** as $\rightarrow \sqrt{\frac{k}{md}} eV \leftarrow$ meaning that when two Photons strike each other then the

Produced Work is kept in the cave , r , as fundamental frequency $f_1 = n \frac{\sigma\Phi}{2\pi r}$, and which is equal to **The Eigenvalues and Eigenvectors of the Photons-Heap** .

Above Procedure and because of their **common Inertia of Atoms-masses** allows us to accept the **angular- velocities of each Atom separately** , This Property also exists in Atoms Bonding .

Figure - 9 - : The Stability of Photon as Electromagnetic Wave with the Two frequencies .

The Dual Property of The **Simultaneous existence** as Electric and as Magnetic Fields in wavelengths , λ_x , λ_y , as **Effective Range** .which is thrusted through the Newton's Gravitational Force G , only becomes from the Trigonometry relations ,

$$\sin(2\phi) = \sin(\pi - 2\phi) = \sin(\frac{\pi}{2} - \phi) \text{ and from Physics } E_x = g ,$$

5... Maxwel Electric Displacement current $\partial D / \partial t$ is created from (c_x , c_y) Vectors motion , which happens from the gravity continuous action which produces the Work $W = c_y g$, Since E-W , M-W , are both the Resultance of circular -frequencies W_R , it reveals the coupling of motion $\{ E-W \} \rightarrow \partial \sqrt{c_x^2 + c_y^2} / \partial t$, $\{ M-W \} \rightarrow \partial \sqrt{c_x^2 + c_y^2} / \partial t$, $\{ E-W \}$.

This means that the Source-charge of Electromagnetic waves are the Vectors = Resultants E-W , M-W , where $W_{RX}, W_{RY} = \vartheta \sqrt{c_x^2 + c_y^2} / \vartheta t$, and $W_{RZ} = \sqrt{c_x^2 + c_y^2} = \bar{c}$, and are E-W = The Kinetic Energy and M-W = The Potential Energy Propagating from one Position to another without any matter being transferred . Both are Propagated by the action of the Gravity , $g. c_y$ which exists without mass , through Gravity-Field-medium continuously only. The Dual-Property of Particles and Waves allow Electromagnetic waves to Propagate in an definite direction and simultaneously to Propagate themselves along , and independently of the medium , and this because are created by the vibration of an electric charge [\oplus, \ominus] .

9..C. The Total Energy in Loops : [79]

It was shown in [58] that the maximum velocity in a closed System occurs in Common circle , when the two velocities , \bar{c}, \bar{v} are Perpendicular between them , and are not Producing Work from where then dispersion follows Pythagoras theorem and the Resultant Quantized linear Space length , r , becomes , as the Resultant of Energy Vectors as follows ,

$$r = |(\bar{c}.T)| = \sqrt{v^2 + c^2} \text{ and by using Space Vector } \bar{r} = |(\bar{c}.T)| = \sqrt{v^2 + c^2} \text{ then The total Rotating Energy is } \rightarrow \pm \bar{\Lambda} = \bar{p}.r = (M.c).r = (M.c). \sqrt{v^2 + c^2} \text{ and by squaring both sites } \\ [\pm \bar{\Lambda}]^2 = p^2. r^2 = M^2. c^2. (v^2+c^2) = (M^2.v^2) . c^2 + M^2.c^4 = (p^2.c^2) + M^2.c^4 = \\ = [p.c]^2 + [m_o.c^2]^2 \text{ or is } \mathbf{E_T = E_R + E_K} \rightarrow \text{i.e.}$$

Total - Energy of Elementary-Particle = Intrinsic Rotational + Kinetic Energy ,

The velocity of Elementary Particles is the light velocity $c = v = 2\pi r. f_e$ and the

frequency $\rightarrow f_e = \frac{c}{2\pi.r}$ (a) Rotational Energy $E_R = \bar{B} . \bar{w} = 2L = J.w^2$ and

$$\rightarrow E_R = \left[\frac{\pi r^4}{8} \right]. \left[\frac{c^2}{r} \right] = \frac{\pi c^2}{8} r^3 = 3,53535.10^{16}. r^3 \dots\dots\dots(b)$$

Energy and frequency of Elementary Particles can be found from cave r , only since , c ,

$$\text{constant , and Total-Energy } \rightarrow E_T = E_R + E_K = \frac{\pi c^2}{8} r^3 + \frac{1}{2} m.v^2 = 3,535.10^{16}. r^3 + \frac{1}{2} m.v^2 \dots(c)$$

The mass of Elementary Particles is $m = \frac{E}{2r^2.w^2} = \frac{J.w^2}{2} . \frac{1}{2r^2.w^2} = \frac{J}{4.r^2} = \frac{\pi.r^2}{16}$, i.e. it is dependent

on Radius of Cave , and for cave $r = 10^{-62}$ mass $\rightarrow m = \frac{\pi.10^{-124}}{16} = 1,935. 10^{-125}$ kg.

When The SPACE acquires ENERGY as Velocity then becomes an Energy-monad . [26]

Applying Quaternion equation $[-\nabla\Lambda, \nabla\Lambda] = 0$ for Point ,O, and for constant velocity , \bar{c} , then issues $[-\nabla c, \nabla xc] = 0$ where $[-\nabla c] \perp [\nabla xc]$ which means that it is a Mechanism that instantly transports Breakage-masses in two directions Dynamically and Perpendicularly to all Inertial frames Layers . From their Velocity-Energy vector are Produced the Three Breakages as ,

$$[\pm s^2 = \pm (wr)^2] , \text{ and } [\nabla i = 2(wr)^2] \text{ and from them subatomic Particles } \rightarrow \text{Fermion and Bosons .}$$

Rotating energy is $\rightarrow \pm \bar{\Lambda} = \bar{p}.r = (M.c).r = (M.c). \sqrt{v^2 + c^2}$ and squaring both sites

$$[\pm \bar{\Lambda}]^2 = p^2.r^2 = M^2.c^2.(v^2+c^2) = (M^2.v^2).c^2 + M^2.c^4 = (p^2.c^2) + M^2.c^4 = \\ [p.c]^2 + [m_o.c^2]^2 \text{ or is } \mathbf{E_T = E_R + E_K} \rightarrow \text{i.e.}$$

Total - Energy of Elementary-Particle = Intrinsic Rotational + Kinetic Energy ,

a).. Dot Product and Cross Product :

The Dot-Product happens for interactions between Similar dimensions ,while the Cross-product between Different-dimensions. Cross-product of any two vectors \bar{a}, \bar{b}

is $\bar{a} \times \bar{b} = |\bar{a}|.|\bar{b}| \sin \theta . \bar{n}$ and for $\bar{a} = \bar{b}$ and $\theta = 90^\circ$ then $\bar{a} \times \bar{a} = \bar{a}^2$, and for

Quaternion , s , which performs the Work of rotating the one vector around the other

→ Work = $\bar{a} \times \bar{a} = \bar{a}^2 \cdot \bar{r}$, and for $\bar{a} = \bar{v}$ then, Work = $\bar{v}^2 \cdot \bar{r} = |\bar{v}| \cdot |\bar{v}| \cdot \bar{r} = v^2 \cdot r \cdot \bar{n}$
 = $(w r)^2 r \cdot \bar{n} = (2\pi r/T)^2 r \cdot \bar{n} = (4\pi^2 r^2 / T^2) \cdot r \cdot \bar{n} = \frac{4\pi^2 r^3}{T^2} \cdot \bar{n} = (4\pi^2 r^2 \cdot f^2) \cdot r \cdot \bar{n}$, or(w)

Work = $4\pi^2 \frac{r^3}{T^2} \cdot \bar{n} = 4\pi^2 \cdot r^3 \cdot f^2 \cdot \bar{n}$, which is the Kepler celestial law for *microcosm*.

Since in Mechanics issues $z^2 = s^2 - s^2 + 2.s.s = 1$, and from Unit-quaternion $s^2 + [iv]^2 = 1$ then is → $s^2 - v^2 = 1$ (d) Equation (d) is a **Cone relation** on where Total-energy, Kinetic and Potential is conserved and for Photon, Electromagnetic radiation is the Kinetic-energy and the Velocity-vector-Energy - tank is the Potential. Photon is an Energy-store, r , in a Stationary-wave of wavelength $n\lambda = 2r$ consisted of n stationary lobes filled in λ with inner motion the Electromagnetic - Displacement-current and Outward the Propagating, Energy-store $\lambda = 2r/n$, with the light speed, c , the two transverse fields, {the + Electric-field and the - Magnetic-field}. Equation (w) declares the relation between the *Total-Energy* W in caves, and the *Geometry* of Energy=cave Space $r \equiv [EM-R \equiv f_{1=N}, f_2, f_3, f_D, f_n]$ with a binding constant, *proved to be the g*.

The United-Coulomb-Newton Law for Interactions :

For a Stationary interaction the *Coulomb-Law-Force* is $F_C = \frac{k[q_1 q_2]}{r^2}$, and for Charges q_1, q_2 where Constant $k = 9.0.10^9 \text{ N.m}^2/\text{C}^2$, and r , is the distance between the Charges.

For a Stationary interaction *Newton Law for masses* m_1, m_2 is $F_N = \frac{G[m_1 m_2]}{r^2}$, and for $\bar{v} = \bar{r}$

Conjugating Interaction, **Energy** $E = \frac{v^2}{2}[m_1 + m_2] = \frac{r^2}{2} [\frac{F_1}{g} + \frac{F_2}{g}] = \frac{F \cdot r^2}{2} [\frac{1}{g} + \frac{1}{g}] = \frac{F \cdot r^2}{2} [\frac{g+g}{g \cdot g}] = \frac{F \cdot r^2}{2} [\frac{2 \cdot g}{g^2}] = \frac{F_N \cdot r^2}{g}$, where F_N is Newton Force, and E is the Energy of the Field-System.

Equating the **two forces** then $\frac{k[q_1 q_2]}{r^2} = \frac{gE}{r^2}$, or → $k [q_1, q_2] = g \cdot E$ (1)

Equation (1) relates any two Charges q_1, q_2 , with Field-Energy E , under vector $\bar{v} = \bar{r} = \bar{c}$

The Gravitational force G and Stresses σ : [77]

From A-7 In Planck's cave, the *Least-Unit-Energy-cave* is that of **Hydrogen-Cave H**, and Issues $g \cdot r^3 \cdot f_p^2 = 1$, or $g = [\frac{1}{r^3 \cdot f_p^2}] = [\frac{T_p^2}{r^3}]$. The Earth constant $k_E = 6,8116.10^{-12}$, and

The Gravitational-Constant-Force G, becomes as **Stress** \equiv Force/Area $\equiv g$, as equation $G = g k_E = g \cdot [g_E k_E] = [\frac{T_p^2}{a^3}] \cdot [g_L k_L] = [\frac{c \cdot r^3}{a^3}] \cdot [g_L k_L] = 9,8076925 * 6,8116.10^{-12} \equiv$

$6,68056.10^{-11} \frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{Ns}^2}$, and **Effects on gravity** → $g \equiv 9,8076925$ as **Stress** $\frac{\text{Kg}}{\text{cm}^2}$ [73]

The Beyond-Planck-length Force $F = \sigma \cdot A =$ The Glue-Bond \equiv Stress x Area $\equiv [\frac{2\pi f \cdot r}{\Phi}] \cdot A = w r \cdot [\frac{A}{\Phi}] = \bar{v} [\frac{A}{\Phi}]$, and becomes a moving Storage $\frac{A}{\Phi}$ travelling with velocity n times that of light-velocity c , as equation $\bar{v} = n c$.

1.. For The Beyond-Planck-Length Force issues → $F = \Phi^3 \cdot [\oplus \sigma \ominus] = \sigma \times \Phi^3$ where,

$\sigma \equiv [\oplus \sigma \ominus] \equiv$ The Stress of Cave as the Quantized distance $r \rightarrow [\oplus \leftarrow r \rightarrow \ominus]$

and $\Phi = \frac{(1+\sqrt{5})}{2}$ is the mould of Quantization, a *kind of Impedance in Electricity*, and

in Material-Points frequency $f = \frac{c}{2\pi r} = 2,93949410^{42}$ H, and $\sigma = \frac{c}{\Phi}$.

2.. For the In Planck-Length- G-Force as Stress $\sigma = \frac{2\pi r f}{(n)\Phi} = \frac{2\pi r f}{1 \cdot \Phi} = \frac{2\pi \cdot 1,616199 \cdot 10^{-35} \cdot 2,93949410^{42}}{1,6180339}$

$= 1,84456315 \cdot 10^8 \text{ t/m}^2 = 1,84456315 \cdot 10^{11} \text{ Kg/m}^2$, and the Angular velocity, w , from Total Planck Cave is $|w| = \frac{\sigma}{2r} [1+\sqrt{5}] = (\frac{1,852816510^{11}}{2 \cdot 1,616199 \cdot 10^{-35}}) \cdot 1,6180339 = 9.274599 \cdot 10^{46}$, rad/sec and

3.. For the Outer-Planck-Length- G-Force as Stress $\sigma = \sigma_{p1} = 1,84456315 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ Kg/m}^2$,

and , $G = \sigma \times \Phi^3 \equiv [1,84456315 \cdot 10^{-11}] \cdot [3,6180339887] = 6,673692 \cdot 10^{-11} \frac{m^3}{Ns^2}$, Nevertheless

For Earth-System mass $M_E = 5,9723 \cdot 10^{24}$ Kg , and for the Area \rightarrow Radius 6378,137 Km
 $= 6,378 \cdot 10^6$ m , then Earth-constant $k_E = \frac{[6,378 \cdot 10^6]^2}{5,9723 \cdot 10^{24}} = 6,8115518 \cdot 10^{-12}$ and Gravitational
 Force $G = g \cdot k_E \equiv g \cdot [g_L k_L] \equiv [\frac{T^2 P}{a^3}] \cdot [g_L k_L] \equiv 9,80769 \cdot 6,8115518 \cdot 10^{-12} \equiv 6,68056 \cdot 10^{-11} \frac{m^3}{Ns^2}$

Remarks :

- The Stresses become from a Force and a Surface as equation $\sigma = \frac{F}{A}$, and in the case of Gravitational constant G and a cave , r , then $\rightarrow \sigma = \frac{G}{4\pi r^2} = \frac{G}{\pi(2r)^2} = \frac{G}{\pi s^2}$, or a vector $|\vec{S}|$. Above relation means that Force **G** needs a Vector-Surface $\pi \cdot s^2$ to be spread as Stress σ which is the case of Constant-light-velocity **c** as \Rightarrow , or $\Uparrow c_{E \perp M}$. [96]
- The case of a vector **s** , is the **Linear-Stress** while of an Plane is the **Surface-Stress** and consequently of a Volume is a **Space-Stress** , as this was referred before for **G** Force , i.e. $G \equiv \sigma \cdot \Phi^3 \equiv \Phi^2 \cdot \{ \sigma \Phi \} \equiv 2\pi f_p r \equiv w r \equiv \bar{v} \equiv m a = \bar{c} = [\frac{2 \cdot B}{\pi r^3}]$ are all Energy-Vectors .
- Since Stresses follow equation $\sigma = \frac{F}{A} = \frac{2\pi r f}{\Phi}$, conclusively since all **Forces and Areas** are every-where and are related to their-cave **r** , through their frequency , **f** , therefore it is the mean of motion for **every-Information** .

10.C.. SUMMARY OF PRIOR : [87]

1.. Gravitational-Constant-Force **G** , becomes as Stress \equiv Force/Area \equiv g , as equation

$$G = g k_E = g \cdot [g_L k_L] = [\frac{T^2 P}{a^3}] \cdot [g_L k_L] = [\frac{c \cdot r^3}{a^3}] \cdot [g_L k_L] = 9,808238 * 6,8116 \cdot 10^{-12} \equiv 6,68056 \cdot 10^{-11} \frac{m^3}{Ns^2}$$

and Effects on gravity , $g \equiv 9,808238$ Stress $\frac{Kg}{cm^2}$

2.. Spin of Photon $4S \equiv 4|\vec{B}| \equiv \pi \cdot r^3 \sigma \Phi \equiv B_p \equiv [EM-R \equiv f_{1=N}, f_2, f_3, f_D, f_n = w^2 \equiv \pi \frac{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma}{4\pi r}]$

$$[\frac{(\pi r^2)^2 f}{2}] = \frac{\sigma}{2\pi r} \Phi \equiv L = - a \cdot \sqrt{2E} .$$

When enters in minimum-Energy cave $a = 2,1145016 \cdot 10^{-11}$ m

creates the **Hydrogen cave** = - 13,6 eV , and from the Unit-Orbit equation , $\ddot{x} + w^2 x = 0$, the Quantum relation $k = g [f^2 \cdot \pi^3] = 1$ and the Energy Orbits f_n .

From Photon-charge -relation , $\bar{q}_{\text{Photon}} = \frac{G}{\sqrt{2} \cdot f} = \frac{G \cdot h}{\sqrt{2} \cdot E} = 2,763 \cdot 10^{-24}$ Coulomb .

3.. Gravity $g \cong \sigma = \frac{\text{Force}}{\text{Area}} = \frac{\text{Mass}}{\text{Area}} = \frac{G}{k}$, while Gravity force $[\nabla i] \equiv F_G \equiv m_G g = g \cdot \nabla [\frac{\sigma}{c^2}]^2 \cdot r$

$$= m_G \frac{v^2}{r} = J w^2 \cdot g_G = [\frac{\pi r^4}{2}] w^2 \cdot \frac{v^2}{r} = \frac{v^2}{r} [\frac{\pi r^4}{2}] \frac{v^2}{r^2} = [\frac{\pi r v^4}{2}]$$

and from Spin-Momentum relation

$$S = \vec{B} = \frac{E}{w} = \frac{E}{2\pi f} = \frac{Er}{\sigma \Phi} = \frac{rG}{\sigma \Phi}$$

then $\vec{B}^2 = \frac{r^2 \sigma^2}{r^2} \Phi^2$, and $\rightarrow [\vec{B}]^2 = [\frac{\Phi \sigma}{r}]^2 \leftarrow$ while as

centripetal \rightarrow Gravity-force $F_G \equiv m_G g = g \cdot \nabla [\sigma c]$. $r = m_G \frac{c^2}{r} = J w^2 \cdot g_G = \frac{v^2}{r} [\frac{\pi r^4}{2}] \frac{v^2}{r^2} = \frac{\pi r v^4}{2}$ and

$$\text{from } f^5 = \frac{\pi g}{[2\pi r]^3} \rightarrow f^2 = \frac{\pi g}{[2\pi r]^3} = \frac{\pi g}{[v \cdot w r]^3} = \frac{\pi g}{[v = n \cdot \pi \cdot c]^3} = \frac{\pi g}{[n \cdot \pi \cdot c]^3}$$

and defines the ,

Black-Hole-Gravity-equation related to the Inner Quantum-velocity v , and to its n lobes .

$$\text{Gravity-Acceleration is } g_G = s \left[\frac{\pi r v^4}{2} \right] = \left[\frac{3,1415926([\sqrt{5}+1] \cdot \sqrt[4]{2} \cdot 10^{-35}) \cdot (299793458)^4}{2} \right] \cdot e^3 =$$

$$6,044981 \cdot 10^{-35} \cdot 80,776078 \cdot 10^{32} \cdot 20,085536 = g_G = 9,8076925 .$$

From the Primary equation of Electron $\rightarrow \mathbf{w}_e \cdot \mathbf{m}_e = \pi g = \text{constant} \equiv \text{Energy} \equiv$
 [meter of area * meter of force] \equiv Electrons on Orbits, on Traces and also the Unit
 Space \equiv Massive-United-Unit-Space $\equiv \rightarrow [+ \bar{v} \cdot s^2] \leftarrow$ The Nucleus jointed through the
 Neutral Material-Points [(+) [\leftrightarrow] (-)] with the Strong-force $\rightarrow S_F = h \cdot f_n \equiv h \cdot \{ [S \equiv B_P$
 $\equiv \text{EM-R} \equiv f_{1=N}, f_2, f_3, f_D, f_n = w^2] \equiv h \cdot n \frac{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma}{4\pi r} \equiv h \frac{n\sigma \cdot \bar{B}}{8 r^2} \dots\dots\dots (\text{mg})$

Equations (mg) are the Energy-Space-constituents in the Hydrogen-System .

From relation $f_n = \frac{[(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma]}{4\pi r}$ and $\bar{B} = \frac{\pi r^3 \sigma}{8} [1+\sqrt{5}]$ then Force f_n Orient Spin \bar{S} to \bar{B} as ,

$$\bar{g} = f_n \times \bar{B} = \sigma |f_n| \times |\bar{B}| \cdot \sin \theta = \frac{[(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma]}{4\pi r} \frac{\pi r^3 \sigma}{8} [1+\sqrt{5}] \cdot 1 = \frac{[\sigma^2 r^2 (1+\sqrt{5})^2]}{32} \equiv \frac{\sigma^2 r^2 \cdot \Phi^2}{8} \dots(\text{g})$$

4.. The Unit-Hydrogen-frequency f_e , in Stress g , Originates Electron-mass m_e from

$$\text{equation } 4\pi f_e^2 \cdot m_e = g, \text{ and from } G, \text{ Electron-Charge } \bar{q}_E = \frac{G}{c\sqrt{2}} = 1,58 \cdot 10^{-19} \text{ C}$$

5.. Strong-Force $S_F = \left| \frac{g}{r^2} \right| \left| \bar{E} \right| = \left| \frac{g}{r^2} \right| \left| \frac{\pi}{g r^2} [g^2 r + 2 \cdot L^2 \cdot f^2] \right| = \frac{\pi}{r^4} [g^2 r + 2 \cdot L^2 \cdot f^2]$ depend on \bar{E} ,

$$\text{found in our Sun, for Proton-Bonding as frequency } f^5 = \frac{g}{[2\pi a]^3}$$

6.. From Orbit-equation $g [f^2 \pi^3] = 1$, Electron-charge $\bar{q}_E = g [k_E / c\sqrt{2}]$, Nutation

$$\text{Energy } E = g \left[\frac{M \cdot m^2}{2 S^2} \right] \cdot [2k + Mm] \equiv g \frac{k_o}{2 S^2}, \text{ Nut-Frequency } f_N = f_R = g \left[\frac{s \cdot m_e}{2\pi \cdot J_3 \cdot w} \right] \text{ is Seen}$$

7.. The Strong-close-Energy $E = \left\{ \frac{k}{r} + \frac{L^2}{2m r^2} \right\} = \frac{\pi}{g r^2} [g^2 r + 2L f^2]$ is for Force $S_F = \left| \frac{g}{r^2} \right| \left| \bar{E} \right|$ i.e.

The effect of Gravity, g , Is on All Energy-structures and it is the Resonance frequency f_R of, ELECTRON Charge, \vec{e} , and of Spin \vec{S} . The Produced Work as frequency f_R is Conserved in the Caves. The difference between Potential-Energy of the Orbit and that of the Electron-Nutation in Electron-Precession-motion is the lowest Potential-Energy, Resonance-Energy as Resonance-Frequency f_R . [82]. R-F $\rightarrow f_R$, IS the Energy in [Bracket-Orbit-Hook] which Joints the Atoms .

8.. In [82] is presented the Circular Planetary-motion where the constant velocity from

$$\text{Orbit-Geometry is equal to } v = \mathbf{v}_p = \omega r \text{ and the Centripetal-acceleration } \mathbf{a}_p = \frac{v^2}{r}.$$

The Elliptical motion after collision, where the acceleration is increased, the velocity is equal

$$\text{to } \mathbf{v}_p^2 = 4 \pi^2 a^3 \cdot f_p^2 \cdot \left[\frac{1+e}{r} \right] \text{ and the Centripetal acceleration } \mathbf{a}_p = - \frac{32 \cdot C^2 a^2}{r^5} = - \frac{32 \cdot \pi \cdot a^4 [1]}{T^2 r^4 [r^5]},$$

where for $r = a \rightarrow a_p = -\frac{32\pi}{T^2 r^5}$, and $C = \frac{dS}{dt} = r^2 \cdot d\phi / 2 = \text{constant} = \text{The Area swept in equal}$

times of radius Orbit-Nucleus . For Circular , Elliptical , Parabola , Hyperbola motion after collision , where then acceleration is increased and the velocity is equal to $p = \text{parameter}$,

$$\mathbf{v}_p^2 = 4\pi^2 \frac{a^3}{T^2} \left[\frac{1+e}{r} \right] = 4\pi^2 a^3 f_p^2 \left[\frac{1+e}{r} \right] = \frac{4C^2}{p} \left[\frac{2}{r} - \frac{1-e^2}{p} \right] = k \left[\frac{2}{r} - \frac{1}{a} \right] \text{ and Centripetal-acceleration}$$

$$\mathbf{a}_p = \frac{d^2 r}{dt^2} - \frac{4c^2}{z^3}, \text{ where } k = \frac{4C^2}{p} = \text{constant}, \frac{d^2 r}{dt^2} = \text{The Natural acceleration}$$

Velocity equation in a Central-motion is $v^2 = 4C^2 \cdot \left[\frac{e^2 \sin^2 \phi}{p} + \frac{1}{r^2} \right] \dots (f-4)$ where constant

$C = \frac{\pi ab}{T} = \pi ab f_p = \frac{dS}{dt} = r^2 d\phi / 2 \equiv \text{The covered orbiting area per time second}$, and

derivative $\frac{d(1/r)}{d\phi} = -\frac{e \sin \phi}{p}$. From Planet-Nucleus ... (a-1) , $r = \frac{p}{1+e \cos \phi}$ and velocity is ,

$$v^2 = 4C^2 \cdot \left[\frac{e^2 \sin^2 \phi}{p^2} + \frac{1+e^2 \cos^2 \phi + 2e \cos \phi}{p^2} \right] = \frac{4C^2}{p^2} [e^2 + 1 + 2e \cos \phi] = \frac{4C^2}{p} \left[\frac{e^2 + 1}{p} + \frac{2}{r} - \frac{2}{p} \right] =$$

$$v^2 = \frac{4C^2}{p} \left[\frac{2}{r} - \frac{1-e^2}{p} \right] \dots (f5), \text{ and for ellipse issuing } 2a = r_{\phi=0} + r_{\phi=a} = \frac{p}{1+e} + \frac{p}{1-e} = \frac{2p}{1-e^2}$$

therefore , Velocity from Geometry $\rightarrow v^2 = \frac{4C^2}{p} \left[\frac{2}{r} - \frac{1-e^2}{p} \right] = \frac{4C^2}{p} \left[\frac{2}{r} - \frac{1}{a} \right] \dots (f-6)$

From (f-6) , when Planet is at Perihelion near the Focus then $\frac{1}{r} = \frac{1+e}{p}$, and velocity is

$$v^2 = \frac{4C^2}{p} \left[\frac{2}{r} - \frac{1-e^2}{p} \right] = \frac{4C^2}{p} \left[\frac{2}{r} - \frac{1-e}{r} \right] = \frac{4C^2}{p} \left[\frac{1+e}{r} \right], \text{ where } k = \frac{4C^2}{p} = \frac{4(\pi ab/T)^2}{b^2/a} = 4\pi^2 \frac{a^3}{T^2} \dots (f-7)$$

then Kepler constant , K , is as below and for $e = \sqrt{1 + 2EL^2/G^2M^2m^3}$, velocity

$$v^2 = 4\pi^2 \frac{a^3}{T^2} \left[\frac{1+e}{r} \right] = [4\pi^2 \cdot a^3 f_p^2] \cdot \left[\frac{1+e}{r} \right] = [4\pi^2 \cdot C] \cdot \left[\frac{1+e}{r} \right] = K \left[\frac{1+e}{r} \right] \dots (f-7a)$$

From Mechanics Velocity $v = \dot{r} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{m} [E - V(r) - \frac{L^2}{2m r^2}]} \equiv \sqrt{\frac{2}{m} [E - \{ \frac{k}{r} + \frac{L^2}{2m r^2} \}]}$ and

$$v^2 = \frac{2}{m} [E - \{ \frac{k}{r} + \frac{L^2}{2m r^2} \}] = [4\pi^2 \cdot k] \cdot \left[\frac{1+e}{r} \right] \leftrightarrow E = \{ \frac{L^2}{2m r^3} + \frac{k}{r} [1 + 2\pi^2 m k (1+e)] \} \dots (f-8)$$

Remark-1 \rightarrow Hydrogen Atom with One Nucleus of Spin $\{ +\frac{1}{2} \}$ and one Electron in

Energy-Orbit of Spin $\{ -\frac{1}{2} \}$, **Is a Nucleus-Orbit-Magnet** $\equiv \oplus \text{Proton} \leftrightarrow \ominus \text{Electron}$ which **ORIGINATES The-Constant-Resonance-frequency** f_R between them , becoming from the Eternal-changeable-motion of the Electron around the Nucleus and from the **Produced** Variable – Magnetic - Orbital-Fields.

Since the Total-Spin in Hydrogen is measured and at the Nucleus-Position then , Protons Absorb Energy from The-Electron-Spin which is moving in its different directions , **and Store it as a Resonance-frequency** f_R , IN ORBIT - RIM N-O .

This Orbit-Rim which is [**The** , m_N , m_e , **Current-loop**] , continually increase its Energy and so produces a Signal in the Hydrogen-Atom , i.e.

Gravity g , acting On The Varying-Velocity \dot{x} of the **Orbiting-Electron Crates Work which is Conserved as Electron-Magnetic-Field** , magnetic moment $\bar{\mu}$, in a time **T** , and as a **Resonance-frequency f_R** .

When velocity $\dot{x} = 0$ then $E = U(x)$, i.e. the Signal is the Increasing-Potential Energy in loop .**The** [m_N , m_e , **Current-loop**] consists the **Energy-Bond** between Atoms and is the **Communication-tool** , *The Resonance Signal* , in all Universe. In case of **An-External-Magnetic - Field** , **Electron-Spin is swigging around the Magnetic-Vector** and this Motion , *the Nutation* , is transferred to the Nucleus.

The Produced-Work as Frequency $f_N = \frac{sQ}{2\pi J_3 w} \equiv f_R = 2,8398447 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

IN MRI , this is the Transverse-Precession , where B-Vector creates an RF - Signal from the Precessing Protons , and **Conserved Energy is the frequency $f_N = f_R$** .

Because of the Magnetic-field created On-Orbit and Applied at-Nucleus with the same Effect then , exists LARMOR Equation as , $w_0 = \gamma \cdot \beta_0 / 2\pi$, and for Hydrogen at 1,5 T Magnet , $\gamma = 2,675 \cdot 10^8 / \text{sT}$, $\beta_0 = 1,5 \text{ T}$, then an-frequency $w = 63,864 \text{ MHz} = 63,864 \cdot 10^8 \text{ Hz}$, the frequency $f_N = 2\pi \cdot w = 4,012575 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Remark - 2 → On Figure -13 : [87]

BONDING , $f_N = \frac{sQ}{2\pi J_3 w}$, Happens in the **Maximum-Potential cave**

$E = -U(x)$, which is needed for any **Two Atoms to Joint** and create **molecules** .

Resonance Phenomena in any Media (Mechanical , Electrical , Acoustic , Magnetic) is that , for Response is the maximum at a Specific-frequency f_R and **requires more Energy Input** including that frequency . Nucleus with Spin $S \neq 0$ can absorb and emit Electromagnetic Radiation and undergo , **Resonance**, when placed in a magnetic field.

This Uniform-Magnetic-field of Nucleus-Orbit [$p \leftrightarrow e$] already exists in Protons which Eternally becomes from the Swinging of the **Electron-Angular-velocity-Cone** , with **Spin-Vector \bar{S}** in the axis of cone as **Angular-Momentum-Vector** , *the Polhode* , at a fixed Point of the **Central-Cone-circle** . Because of Gravity **g** , **SPIN ψ** is under **NUTATION $\hat{\theta}$** , and the **Response** is the **PRECESSION $\hat{\phi}$** , or

THE → **ELECTRON-NUTATION** ← due to Gravity is applied for a short time in the **Plane Perpendicular** , \perp , to the **variated Moment-Vector** , $|\bar{R}| \equiv |\bar{M}_T| = |\bar{M}_N| + |\bar{M}_O|$ and the Work produced is **Conserved** in → Nucleus - Orbit [$p \leftrightarrow e$] \equiv the **Energy-Box**.

The angular velocity-cone \bar{w} , is Rolling with Spin-Vector \bar{B} in the central cone.

The difference between the Potential-energy of the Orbit and that of the Electron-Nutation Precession with the lowest Potential energy , is the **Resonance -Frequency \equiv The Energy** .

In figure 11, is shown the **Magnetic-Dipole-moment** of nucleus which is associated with the Orbital angular momentum , $\bar{B} = \text{the Spin}$. When an external **Static-Magnetic-field** is present then Spectral-lines Split into multiple closely-spaced-lines. As was calculated the **Strength of a Magnetic-field** of 1 Tesla is $\text{Static-M} = 1,174462 \cdot 10^{-4} = 11,74462 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ eV}$. In the Absence of Electron $|\bar{M}_T| \equiv |\bar{M}_N|$ *the Spin* , and exists The Nucleus-Magnetic-field \bar{B}_L .

1.C... The Origination of Spin \bar{B} :

It is an Application to Material-Points [$\oplus \leftrightarrow \ominus$] , by considering the Positive-constituent with angular velocity $\bar{w} = \bar{v} / r = \frac{\sigma}{2r} [1 + \sqrt{5}] \dots\dots\dots(1)$ [70] and for an angle 45° from , **x** , axis , where then the Ellipsoid of Angular-velocity is Perpendicular to the Plane of motion .

Moment of Inertia to , **z** , axis is that of sphere equal to $J_3 = \frac{\pi r^4}{4}$ which is the same in all

Principal axes , and exists , $J = J_1 = J_2 = J_3 = \frac{\pi r^4}{4}$, therefore Angular-kinetic-energy \equiv Angular-velocity-Ellipsoid and then becomes , $J_1 w_1^2 + J_2 w_2^2 + J_3 w_3^2 = 2E$ (2)

The Energy-Ellipsoid as $\bar{B} \equiv \text{Spin}$ are , $w_1^2 + w_2^2 + w_3^2 = \frac{2E}{J} = \frac{32 E}{(\pi r^4)^2} = \frac{B^2}{J^2}$.

Angular-momentum \equiv Spin $\equiv \bar{B} \equiv [r \sigma (1+\sqrt{5})]$ (3) In Figure -14- and

for the center , K , of \oplus sphere , issues $\bar{v}_K = [\bar{w} . \bar{r}_K] = [\frac{\sigma(1+\sqrt{5})}{2r} 2r] = \sigma [1+\sqrt{5}]$ and $\bar{B} = \bar{S} = [\bar{r} . m \bar{v}] = [r.m. \sigma(1+\sqrt{5})] / 2$ and for $m=1$ then $\bar{B} = [r \sigma (1+\sqrt{5}) / 2]$. The Interchangeable Ellipsoids of Angular velocity [70-P49] , and Momentum for the same Moment of Inertia is $J_1 = J_2 = J_3 = J$, and Angular Velocity $w_1 = w_2 = w_3 = w$, and Momentum $B_1 = B_2 = B_3 = B$ becomes $3J w^2 = C$ and $3B^2/J = C$ and since for circle $J = \frac{\pi r^4}{4}$ then $\frac{3\pi r^4}{4} w^2 = C = (\frac{3\pi r^4}{4}) w^2 = (\frac{3\pi r^2}{4})(rw)^2 = (\frac{3\pi r^2}{4}) [\frac{\sigma}{2} (1 + \sqrt{5})]^2 = \frac{3\pi r^2 \cdot \sigma^2 [3+\sqrt{5}]}{8} \rightarrow$ *The Ellipsoid of Angular-velocity, \bar{w}* , and $3B^2/J = \frac{3(rmv)^2}{J} = \frac{3(rv)^2}{J} = \frac{3r^2 \cdot \sigma^2 [3+\sqrt{5}]}{2} [\frac{4}{\pi r^4}] = \frac{6 \cdot \sigma^2 [3+\sqrt{5}]}{\pi r^2} \rightarrow$ *The Momentum-Ellipsoid, \bar{B}* .

From equation $3B^2/J = \frac{6 \cdot \sigma^2 [3+\sqrt{5}]}{\pi r^2}$ and $J = \frac{\pi r^4}{4}$ then $B^2 = \frac{\pi r^4}{3.2} \frac{6 \cdot \sigma^2 [3+\sqrt{5}]}{\pi r^2} = 4 \cdot r^2 \sigma^2 \Phi^2$ and

The Angular-momentum In Planck's-Length \equiv Spin $\equiv |\bar{B}| \equiv 2 \cdot r \sigma \Phi = 2 \cdot \pi \cdot r^2 \cdot f \dots (s)$

The value of $|\bar{B}| = [2 \cdot 8,79455 \cdot 10^{-35} \cdot 1,16180339] = 2,845976 \cdot 10^{-34} \{ \text{Kg/m/s} \}$.

For Planck-Length $r_p = 1,61623 \cdot 10^{-35} \sqrt{3\pi} = 8,79455 \cdot 10^{-35} \text{ m}$, velocity $|\bar{v}| = \frac{\sigma}{r} [1+\sqrt{5}]$

and from (s) then \rightarrow **Planck-cave-Stress $\sigma = \frac{\bar{B}}{4r \cdot \Phi} = 1$** , **Total-Energy $2E = [J w]^2$** ,

From $|\bar{v}| = \frac{\sigma}{r} [1+\sqrt{5}] = c = 3 \cdot 10^8 \text{ m/s}$ then , $\sigma = \frac{3 \cdot 10^8}{3,679551 \cdot 10^{34}} = 8,1477332 \cdot 10^{-27} \text{ Kg/m}^2$

$|w| = \frac{\sigma}{2r} [1+\sqrt{5}] = (\frac{8,1477332 \cdot 10^{-27}}{2 \cdot 8,7945510^{-35}}) \cdot 3,2360675 = 1,499 \cdot 10^8$, or $|w| = 1,5 \cdot 10^8 \text{ rad / sec}$,

For $\sigma = 8,147733 \cdot 10^{-27} \text{ Kg/m}^2$ and $\bar{B} = 5,691952 \cdot 10^{-34} \text{ J}$ then , Period $T = \frac{2\pi}{w} = \frac{2\pi r}{v} =$

$\frac{4\pi r}{\sigma(1+\sqrt{5})} = \frac{4\pi \cdot 8,79455 \cdot 10^{-35}}{\sigma(1+\sqrt{5})} = \frac{3,4151}{\sigma} 10^{-34} \text{ s}$, or **Period $T = [\frac{4,191584}{10^9}] \text{ s}$** , and frequency $f = \frac{1}{T}$

i.e. **Planck-frequency $f_1 = 2,38573294 \cdot 10^{34} \text{ Hz}$** . From above issues ,

a).. The Spin of cave , r , is Equal to the Angular-momentum-Vector \rightarrow **Spin $\equiv |\bar{B}| \equiv 2r \sigma \Phi$** which contains and is the Golden-Radius-frequency Φ as Pressure , $\pm \sigma$, in cave r .

b).. In Planck's-length [for light velocity $c = 3 \cdot 10^8 \text{ m/s}$] , **velocity** is $|\bar{c}| = \frac{\sigma}{2} [1+\sqrt{5}] \text{ m/s}$ and in cave $r_p = 8,79455 \cdot 10^{-35} \text{ m}$, the **Pressure $\sigma = \frac{r \cdot c}{[1+\sqrt{5}]} = 8,147733 \cdot 10^{-27} \text{ Kg/m}^2$** .

c).. In Planck's-length the Period of Oscillation is $T = \frac{4\pi r}{\sigma(1+\sqrt{5})} = 4,192 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ s}$, and

Frequency $f_p = \frac{1}{T} = \frac{\sigma(1+\sqrt{5})}{4\pi r} = 2,3857265 \cdot 10^7 \text{ Hz}$, which is the minimum in Planck-cave .

The extreme for stresses is $\sigma_{1,2} = \sigma_1 / 2 \pm (\frac{1}{2}) \cdot \sqrt{\sigma_1^2 + 4 \cdot \sigma_1^2} = \sigma_1 \cdot [1 \pm (\sqrt{5})] / 2 = \sigma \Phi$, velocity $v = w \cdot r = \frac{2\pi}{T} = 2\pi r \cdot f = [\frac{\sigma}{2}] \cdot (1+\sqrt{5})$, frequency $f = \frac{(1+\sqrt{5}) \cdot \sigma}{4\pi r}$, Period $T = \frac{4\pi r}{\sigma(1+\sqrt{5})}$

d).. From Orbit vibration $f_n = \frac{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma}{4\pi r} = \frac{\sigma}{2\pi r} \Phi$, $f_n^2 = \frac{\sigma^2}{4\pi^2 r^2} \Phi^2 = \frac{1}{g \cdot a^3}$ and $g a^3 \Phi^2 = \frac{4\pi^2 a^2}{\sigma^2}$, or

$a = \frac{1}{g} [\frac{2\pi}{\sigma \Phi}]^2$ and from Work $W = 2E = B w = J \cdot w^2$, or $2E = 2\pi f$ and $\bar{B} f = \frac{E}{\pi}$ and Energy

in Planck-scale-cave $2E = \bar{B} f_n = [\frac{(1+\sqrt{5})\sigma}{4\pi r}] \cdot \bar{B} = [\frac{\sigma}{2\pi r}] \cdot \bar{B} \Phi$, or $E = [\Phi \frac{\sigma}{4\pi r}] \cdot \bar{B}$ i.e.

Energy in Planck-cave-Particles is dependent on their Spin only , and for Electron $r = a_e$
 $E = [\Phi \frac{\sigma}{4\pi r}].\bar{B} = 1,6180339 [(\frac{1}{4\pi \cdot 1,6840307 \cdot 10^{-17}})]. 2,845976 \cdot 10^{-17} = \frac{21,76 \cdot 10^{-19}}{1,6 \cdot 10^{19}} = 13,6 \text{ eV}$

In frequency , is measured the time needed for the velocity vector to rotate , using the Kepler`s Unit of Time $k = f_e^2 a^3$, the clock measuring the changes of motions .

All above equations define \rightarrow **The Ubiquity of Golden-Ratio- Φ** \leftarrow in all motions

\rightarrow *The Angular-Momentum , Stresses , Frequency or V the vector elocity* in nature . [64-A-B-C]

e).. Generally all Systems Possessing **mass** , *Reaction to any motion or changes* , and

Elasticity , $dl > 0$, are capable of Free-Vibration or **Vibration** that take place in the absence of external excitation . On this Property is based the Programming of the Atoms and their Compounds as is [106]-**Dokimes** with many applications .

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